

Improving local scale prediction of climate change effects on the shallow subsurface temperature field

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Abstract

Groundwater constitutes one of the most important sources of drinking water worldwide. Yet, how the ongoing climate change will affect its quality and availability is a subject of an open debate. In this regard, groundwater temperature plays an influential role in shaping its chemical, biological, and overall quality. The majority of climate models project an air temperature increase of 3 to 5 °C over the next fifty years — how this will translate to the shallow groundwater aquifers remains, however, relatively uncertain, due to the complex physical processes governing heat transport in the shallow subsurface. Consequently, a comprehensive understanding of the interaction between the climate and the shallow subsurface is of utmost importance.

On a regional scale, predictions are typically made relying on numerical models, which often lack in resolution to capture local hydrogeological heterogeneities that may be crucial for accurate simulations of the shallow subsurface temperature field. This study addresses this limitation, by employing high-resolution geological data to better understand the impact of local heterogeneity in the subsurface geology on the shallow temperature field evolution. An analytical solution to the one-dimensional multi-layer advection–diffusion equation with a piecewise temperature signal at the surface was derived, offering a computationally efficient alternative to numerical models. The model was subsequently applied to the study area of Berlin, where groundwater temperature records dating back to 1978 exist, effectively capturing the multi-decadal timescale of the ongoing climate change. The model yields promising results, demonstrating its potential for assessing climate change impacts on shallow groundwater systems and its utility for various sensitivity analyses.

Grundwasser stellt in vielen Ländern eine der wichtigsten Trinkwasserressourcen dar. Wie sich der fortschreitende Klimawandel jedoch auf dessen Qualität und Verfügbarkeit auswirken wird, bleibt abzusehen. Ein entscheidender Einflussfaktor auf die chemische, biologische und allgemeine Beschaffenheit ist die Temperatur des Grundwassers. Die meisten aktuellen Klimamodelle projizieren einen Anstieg der Lufttemperatur um 3 bis 5 °C in den nächsten fünfzig Jahren — wie sich diese Erwärmung jedoch auf die oberflächennahen Grundwasserleiter übertragen lässt, ist aufgrund der komplexen physikalischen Prozesse, die den Wärmetransport im oberflächennahen Untergrund bestimmen, noch relativ ungewiss. Folglich ist ein umfassendes Verständnis der Wechselwirkungen zwischen Klima und oberflächennahem Untergrund von größter Bedeutung.

Auf regionaler Ebene werden Vorhersagen typischerweise mit großskaligen numerischen Modellen getroffen, denen es oft an der geologischen Auflösung mangelt, die erforderlich ist, um lokale Heterogenitäten zu erfassen, welche für präzise Simulationen der Temperaturfelder im oberflächennahen Untergrund entscheidend sein können. Die vorliegende Studie adressiert diese Einschränkung, indem sie lokal hochaufgelöste geologische Daten verwendet, um deren Einfluss auf die Entwicklung des oberflächennahen Temperaturfeldes besser zu verstehen. Es wurde eine analytische Lösung der eindimensionalen mehrschichtigen Advektions-Diffusions-Gleichung mit einem stückweise linearen Temperatursignal an der Oberfläche hergeleitet, die eine rechnerisch effiziente Alternative zu numerischen Modellen darstellt. Das Modell wurde anschließend auf das Untersuchungsgebiet Berlin angewendet, wo Grundwassertemperaturzeitreihen bis ins Jahr 1978 vorliegen, wodurch die mehrjährigen Zeitskalen des anhaltenden Klimawandels erfasst werden. Das Modell liefert vielversprechende Ergebnisse und zeigt sein Potenzial für die Bewertung der Auswirkungen des Klimawandels auf oberflächennahe Grundwassersysteme sowie seinen Nutzen für verschiedene Sensitivitätsanalysen. Um die Anwendbarkeit des Modells vollständig bestimmen zu können, sollten jedoch weitere Grundwassertemperaturdaten im Zusammenhang mit dem Modell untersucht werden.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Groundwater resources in a changing climate

Groundwater is the most important source of available fresh water (Dao et al., 2024), representing around 22 % of all fresh water reserves, or more than 98 % of all liquid fresh water (Fetter, 2001). In comparison to surface water, it is of higher quality while being less sensitive to pollution and seasonal fluctuations (Zektser & Everett, 2004). In addition, groundwater reservoirs are more uniformly spread out over large regions than surface water reservoirs (Zektser & Everett, 2004).

Consequently, groundwater plays a central role in meeting the human water needs. For example, countries like Denmark and Austria rely on groundwater as their only source of drinking water. In most European countries, groundwater meets at least 70 % of the domestic water needs, while still being the main source of drinking water (Zektser & Everett, 2004). Groundwater also plays a crucial role in the energy portfolio, being the main target to exploit hydro-thermal energy. Globally this equates to groundwater covering approximately 50 % of the drinking water needs, 20 % of irrigation needs and 40 % of self-supplied industry needs (Zektser & Everett, 2004).

The ongoing climate change poses a potential threat to the global water resources. Satellite measurements made between the years of 2015 and 2023 showed a decline of around 1200 km³ in both surface water and groundwater in reference to the period between 2002 and 2014 (Riordon, 2025). For comparison, that is 25 times the amount of water stored in Lake Constance (Bodensee). This trend is forecast to worsen by 2050 when up to 57 % of the global population is believed to suffer from water shortage at least one month per year (Unesco, 2018). In addition, climate driven extremes like droughts, are also expected to occur more frequently, increasing the risk of natural disasters such as wildfires (Dao et al., 2024) and food shortages, especially in regions that are heavily reliant on irrigation farming (Riordon, 2025). To further exacerbate these projections, decreasing groundwater levels can lead to the degradation of water quality due to saline-water intrusions and mineral leaching (Earman & Dettinger, 2011).

The majority of climate models predict air temperature to increase by 3 up to 5 °C over the course of the next half a century (Earman & Dettinger, 2011). This trend can already be seen in the trend observed over the last 10 years, which have been the warmest on record (Riordon, 2025). Warming trends in urban areas are further exacerbated due to the so-called Urban Heat Island effect (UHI) (Cubasch & Kadow, 2011) — the surface warming trends in cities are 29 % greater than those in the adjacent rural areas, while generally increasing with city size (Z. Liu et al., 2022).

A changing climate impacts the hydrological cycle in several ways. Precipitation patterns are projected to intensify, resulting in more frequent droughts in dry regions and conversely more frequent floods in wet regions (Dao et al., 2024; Unesco, 2018). Rising average temperatures within the winter months will likely reflect a shift towards rain being the main precipitation form in winter (Reidmiller et al., 2018). On the other hand, rates of evapotranspiration (combination of evaporation and transpiration - water use by plants) are thought to be more stable, although future rates remain relatively uncertain (Earman & Dettinger, 2011). In areas of rapid urbanization, where the natural surface is being replaced with impervious materials, the loss of the evaporative cooling power is the main contributor to the intensified surface warming (Z. Liu et al., 2022).

Given the socio-economic relevance of groundwater, it is of the utmost importance to improve our current understanding on how the ongoing climate change will impact groundwater quality and quantity (Earman & Dettinger, 2011; Riordon, 2025).

1.2 Motivation

With respect to the aforementioned open questions, a key source of uncertainty is to provide an estimate of how increasing surface temperatures will impact groundwater temperature (GWT). GWT has an important effect on biogeochemical processes, mineral weathering and the activity of microorganisms in the shallow subsurface. These processes do interact with one another — for example, a change in the activity of organisms can alter biochemical processes, which in turn alters the chemical composition of groundwater (Dao et al., 2024)). The occurrence of such processes in nature is well documented — in a scientific report by Riedel, 2019 for the German federal state Baden-Württemberg, it was shown how variations in key parameters associated with groundwater quality (including the concentration of carbonic acid) can directly be linked to ongoing temperature changes. Another example of how water temperature affects the release of manganese (Mn), is provided by recent observations done along the river Elbe, Germany, where concentrations of Mn in the water were monitored to rise as high as 0.69 mg L^{-1} during the low discharge season of 2015 (Pauffer et al., 2018). On the other hand, warmer temperatures enhance microorganism growth, further accelerating the breakdown of soil organic material into CO_2 (Dao et al., 2024). Given these observations, an increase in the production cost of drinking water due to heavier purification needs can be expected, while some aquifers potentially can become uninhabitable for crucial groundwater organisms (Riedel, 2019).

Another heat source than the predicted surface warming, is caused by human activities and structures, which are especially relevant in urban areas. For instance, when ground source heat pump systems are used for heating or cooling, local thermal anomalies form due to either heat extraction or injection (Meng et al., 2018). On the other hand, an increasing number of underground structures such as garages, metro tunnels and deep foundations act as a heat bridge between the surface and the shallow subsurface, thus making groundwater in urban areas especially exposed to the aforementioned detrimental effects.

Understanding how GWT will respond to predicted future climatic changes is key to mitigate these impending issues.

1.3 Area of Study- Berlin

Berlin, the capital of Germany, is located in the North German Basin (NGB) — an area encompassing the flat lowlands towards the Baltic Sea in the north, higher terrain of the Hartz Mountains in the south-west and plateaus such as the Kausitzer Grenzwall and High Fläming in the south (Noack et al., 2013). Hosting around 3.9 million inhabitants and covering an area of roughly 891 km^2 it makes it Germany's largest city both in terms of area and population. Surrounded by the federal state of Brandenburg in the north-eastern part of Germany, Berlin is located in one of the driest regions in the country (Pohle et al., 2025).

Figure 1.1: A) Regional placement and B) local topography of the study area

Increasing temperatures in concert with the ongoing shift of precipitation from summer months towards winter months, and more frequent and longer droughts in the summer have all been linked to the undergoing climate change in the region (Pohle et al., 2025). This has been made even more apparent between 2018 and 2023, which were years with the highest average annual air temperatures and lowest annual precipitation on record across many regions in Europe, including Berlin-Brandenburg. This period was followed by a winter season with above average precipitation, which was not enough to replenish the groundwater reservoirs to their pre-2018 levels (Tetzlaff, 2025).

These observations are a cause of concern, as Berlin’s drinking water is extracted almost exclusively within the state borders (Senate Department for the Environment, 2020) — 76 % from bank filtration and the remaining 26 % directly from groundwater (Pohle et al., 2025). In this regard, low groundwater levels are associated with low surface water levels (Tetzlaff, 2025) directly affecting the productive capabilities of bank filtration.

The heavy reliance on groundwater in combination with the current climate change projections and an increasing water demand translate into significant water management challenges. A thorough understanding of the hydrological processes occurring in the shallow subsurface across the wider region is therefore crucial for its sustainable future development.

1.3.1 Groundwater temperatures

Monitoring of groundwater temperature beneath Berlin has been ongoing since 1978. Measurements have revealed that the average GWT has increased by more than 5 °C in comparison to neighboring rural areas (Senate Department for the Environment, 2020). Since 2010, rising temperatures have been increasingly observed in and below the so-called neutral zone — the part of the subsurface where seasonal changes are not detected (approximately 15 to 20 m; Senate Department for the Environment, 2020). As a direct result, the inflection point (the point where temperature starts increasing with depth due to the overall conductive geothermal gradient) is being shifted deeper in the underground. This trend can be clearly observed in Figure 1.2

Figure 1.2: GWT in Berlin at the depth of 20 m in A) 2010, B) 2015 and C) 2020 (Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt Berlin, 2010b, 2015b, 2020b)

In the state of Berlin, there are over 200 locations where GWT is monitored. These monitoring points are essentially open piezometers (a deep piped borehole with a filter at the bottom). In general, GWT profiles are being recorded with a density of 1 measurement per m with an estimated accuracy of ± 0.1 K (Senate Department for the Environment, 2020). Most GWT measurements reach down to a depth of around 60 m, while the number of deeper GWT measurements is more sparse. Additionally, the majority of GWT measurements date back only to 2010, which makes them unsuitable to unravel its changes over a multi-decade timescale. Given these constraints the analysis was narrowed down to 16 GWT points, which provide the required depth and time coverage for this study (see Table 4.1).

1.3.2 Hydrology

In addition to the Spree (the main river in the region) the landscape of Berlin is cut by many smaller rivers, streams, canals, lakes and ponds. The water level in these water bodies is dependent on the surrounding groundwater levels. The fact that the majority of surface water bodies are fed by groundwater makes these surface bodies sensitive to any variations in groundwater levels and therefore to climatic influences (Tsy-pin et al., 2024).

Groundwater levels (GWL) in Berlin are being monitored with the help of more than 900 piezometers (Senate Department for the Environment, n.d.). As can be observed in Figure 1.3, the depth of the

groundwater table varies within the area, correlating with the local topographic elevation — on the higher plateaus in the south and on the north-east end of the city (Barnim plateau and Teltow plateau) it ranges between 7 and 40 m, while in the lowland running from the north-east to the south-east end of the city (Warsaw-Berlin glacial spillway) it ranges from 0 down to a couple of meters (Pohle et al., 2025).

Figure 1.3: Average groundwater depth (from surface) in A) 2010 (Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt Berlin, 2010a) B) 2015 (Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt Berlin, 2015a) and C) 2020 (Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt Berlin, 2020a). The depth was computed with the help of “Digitales Geländemodell – DGM”, 2026

The hydrological make-up underneath the city of Berlin reflects the meteorological events in its major catchments - the Spree catchment (south-east of Berlin) and the Obere Havel catchment (north-west of Berlin) (Pohle et al., 2025). For instance, high evaporation losses in the Spreewald wetlands have significantly influenced the Spree’s stream flow (Pohle et al., 2025) — an effect that is likely to intensify with a warming climate. Additionally, hydrology in the region is shaped by human activities. One example is provided by activities related to lignite mining in the open-pit mines of the Lusatian region — before lignite excavation could begin, groundwater levels first needed to be lowered. The extracted water was then released into the river system, adding significant amounts of water to the stream flow. Mining activity peaked in the 1980s, but has reduced drastically since the German reunification in the 1990s. When the open-pit mines were abandoned, lakes started forming in the pits, drawing significant amounts of water from the nearby river system, a trend that has been reflected in a lower Spree’s stream flow (Pohle et al., 2025).

1.3.3 Climate and surface temperatures

Berlin’s climate is humid continental with an annual average temperature of 9.8 °C and precipitation of 562 mm (for the reference period between 1964-2025) (Pohle et al., 2025), with the temperature displaying a consistently warming trend over the past decades (Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD), 2024). In the century leading up to 2011, the number of days with temperatures below 0 °C has decreased by 17, while an increase of 12 days was observed for days when temperatures reached over 25 °C (Cubasch & Kadow, 2011). In the same period, rainfall in the summer has decreased by roughly 4%, while increasing by around 3% in the winter months. The overall precipitation has barely changed — a decrease of less than 0.2% was observed (Cubasch & Kadow, 2011). Model projections (IPCC A1B) predict an increase of 3 up to 3.5 °C by the end of this century, while the imbalance between summer and winter precipitation will be further amplified, with a projected decrease of 20 to 30% in the summer and an increase of 10 to 20% in the winter (Cubasch & Kadow, 2011).

With that being said, Air Surface Temperature (AST; air temperature measured at 2 m above ground) and Ground Surface Temperature (GST; temperature within the upper soil layer) do not always agree — especially on shorter timescales (Smerdon et al., 2006). One contributing factor is, for instance, the cooling effect associated with soil moisture evaporation, which can significantly influence surface temperatures. The discrepancy between AST and GST can be clearly observed in Figure 1.4. GST is generally the preferred metric when characterizing surface temperature in the context of shallow subsurface modelling as it mitigates many of the uncertainties associated with evapotranspiration. Unfortunately, the earliest available historical GST records date back only to 1991. Consequently, AST records are required to reconstruct historical GST values (see Section 4.2.4).

Figure 1.4: Average Surface Temperatures (ST) in 2022 at 14:00 taken at A) 2m above the surface (AST) and B) in the top soil layer (GST) (Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt Berlin, 2022)

1.3.4 Geology

The shallow subsurface beneath the NGB and therefore Berlin can be grouped into two main geological units — the Quaternary layer and the Tertiary layer. These two units were primarily shaped by glacial activity in the recent past (Pohle et al., 2025). The Quaternary unit consists of alternating layers of sands (glacial, fluvio-glacial, alluvial), gravels, silts, clays and muds (Noack et al., 2013; Pohle et al., 2025; Tsy-pin et al., 2024). From top to bottom (see Figure 1.5), the Tertiary layer can be further divided into 3 sub-units — the post-Rupelian late Tertiary aquifer (sand, silt and clay), the late Tertiary Rupelian-clay aquitard and the early Tertiary-pre-Rupelian aquifer (sand, silt and clay; Noack et al., 2013). The post-Rupelian Tertiary to Quaternary unit is an unconfined porous complex, reaching an average total thickness of approx. 150 m (Pohle et al., 2025). It is bounded along its base by the Tertiary Rupelian-clay aquitard, which hydraulically disconnects it from the deeper Mesozoic saline aquifers (Noack et al., 2013). In areas where glacial erosion was the strongest, the Quaternary unit reaches thicknesses of up to 540 m, cutting deep into the bottom clay unit creating channels through the aquitard (Tsy-pin et al., 2024).

Figure 1.5: Example of the geological cross-section of the shallow subsurface in terms of the main geological units along line A–B (Frick et al., 2019, 2020).

The vertical composition of different soil types in the Quaternary unit varies spatially. Extensive drilling operations carried out in the area provide the source of a vast geological database to characterize the shallow subsurface beneath Berlin. In addition, most of the piezometers active in Berlin (including the 16 GWT points used in this study, see Table 4.1) are paired with a detailed vertical geological profile with a precision in the cm range. These profiles represent a 1D horizontally stratified porous medium as depicted in Figure 1.6.

Figure 1.6: Schematic representation of a unit vertical geological profile consisting of M parallel layers.

1.4 Objectives

To quantify the regional subsurface thermal field variability, studies generally rely on numerical groundwater and heat transport models (Barbieri et al., 2025; Frick et al., 2019; Tsy-pin et al., 2024) — given the spatial scale targeted in these studies, the accuracy of model predictions are limited in depicting local variations as observed across monitoring wells. The caveat here is that our knowledge on the subsurface is limited, thereby introducing large uncertainties into any modelling study. Scientists are therefore asked to make certain generalizations and assumptions in order to overcome these limitations. A lack of detailed geological information of the subsurface, limit the model resolution to the main (macro-)layers, with thicknesses of a couple of 10 to 100 m.

From a monitoring side, scientists can rely on only a handful, if any, boreholes which can provide measurements of subsurface temperatures. Another limitations relates to the duration of those available measurements, which for the majority of available monitoring points, do not cover long enough timescale to capture the subsurface temperature changes induced by the ongoing climate change. All of these issues make the validation of regional models challenging, especially when used for future predictions under different climate prediction models.

Taking advantage of the availability of relatively abundant observational data, this study addresses the following **core scientific question**:

- Can high-resolution subsurface geological data be leveraged within a computationally efficient analytical framework to produce precise and reliable predictions of the shallow subsurface temperature evolution under the ongoing climate change?

This question will be investigated through the following **specific objectives**:

- Develop and validate an analytical model to simulate the one-dimensional heat transport in a stratified porous medium. The model will subsequently be parameterized using high-resolution geological profiles, together with historical records of surface temperature.
- Quantify the influence of geological resolution on the accuracy of subsurface temperature predictions by comparing simulations conducted using high-resolution geological profiles against those employing a coarser parameterization. The working hypothesis is that variations in thermal properties between distinct layers will yield a measurable improvement in the predictions.

Chapter 2

Physical Background

Heat in the shallow subsurface is transported by 2 main mechanisms - advection and diffusion (García Gil et al., 2022), which are described by the following 1D Advection-Diffusion Equation (ADE; Carslaw and Jaeger, 1959; Kurylyk et al., 2014):

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} - U \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = LT \quad x, t \in \mathbb{R}^+ \quad (2.1)$$

where T is temperature (K), t is time (s), x is depth (m) and L is the linear operator of the form $D \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} - U \frac{\partial}{\partial x}$. The bulk thermal diffusivity D ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) and the velocity of the thermal plume U (m s^{-1}) are the two main parameters defining the relative dominance of each transport mechanism, whether diffusion or advection respectively. To quantify these two parameters, it is often useful to consider the spatial scale of the system. Groundwater is stored in aquifers, which have a spatial extent ranging from few up to hundreds of meters. In the context of fluid and heat flow in porous media, this is considered as the macroscopic scale, commonly referred to as the field scale (Ranjbarzadeh & Sappa, 2025). On a smaller scale, a Representative Elementary Volume (REV) can be considered, for which the porous medium can be treated as a continuum material with effective statistical properties (Ranjbarzadeh & Sappa, 2025). Note that in this section, the laws governing fluid and heat flow are provided on an REV scale, where the REV is assumed to be homogeneous and isotropic while assuming Local Thermal Equilibrium (LTE) conditions.

2.1 Diffusion

Heat diffusion is the dominant heat transport mechanism in the shallow subsurface (García Gil et al., 2022). On a REV scale, heat transport by diffusion is described by Fourier's law (García Gil et al., 2022), which leads to the following parabolic equation when all material properties are independent of temperature (Carslaw & Jaeger, 1959):

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - D \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} = 0 \quad (2.2)$$

The bulk thermal diffusivity D ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) is defined as the ratio of the bulk thermal conductivity λ_b ($\text{J s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) and the bulk volumetric heat capacity C_b ($\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$) (Carslaw & Jaeger, 1959):

$$D = \frac{\lambda_b}{C_b} \quad (2.3)$$

λ_b and C_b are effective parameters intrinsic to the material.

2.2 Advection

Advection describes the transport of heat through the porous medium by water flowing through the interconnected pores (García Gil et al., 2022). Mathematically it is described by the following linear hyperbolic partial differential equation of order one:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (2.4)$$

The velocity of thermal plume U (m s^{-1}) is defined as the ratio of groundwater flux (volumetric flow rate per unit area) q ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$), bulk volumetric heat capacity C_b ($\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$) and the volumetric heat capacity of water C_w ($\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$) (Kurylyk et al., 2014):

$$U = q \frac{C_w}{C_b} \quad (2.5)$$

Groundwater flux q is induced by spatial and temporal variation of the hydraulic gradient (Kurylyk et al., 2014). Depending on the rates of q , advection can play an important role in redistributing the diffusive heat in the shallow subsurface. Assuming the solid matrix within an REV as fixed, and under laminar flow conditions, then the pressure gradient and q are linearly related. This relation is commonly referred to as Darcy's law (Ranjbarzadeh & Sappa, 2025; Woessner & Poeter, 2024) and is given as (Woessner & Poeter, 2024):

$$\vec{q} = -K \frac{dh}{dx} \quad (2.6)$$

where K is hydraulic conductivity (m s^{-1}) and h is hydraulic head (m). K represents the relative ease with which groundwater flows through the given porous medium (Woessner & Poeter, 2024). The hydraulic head h is a scalar quantity with a force generating potential, and conversely the hydraulic head gradient dh/dx represents the potential force acting on a unit weight of water, leading to groundwater flow. Hydraulic head gradients result from two main sources — the presence of differences in groundwater pressure p_w (Pa) and the presence of differences in groundwater elevation z (m). Mathematically this can be cast as (Woessner & Poeter, 2024):

$$\frac{dh}{dx} = \frac{d}{dx} \left(z + \frac{p_w}{g\rho_w} \right) \quad (2.7)$$

where g (m s^{-2}) is the gravitational constant. Using atmospheric pressure as reference, p_w above the water table is negative due to capillary forces, at the water table it is zero while below the water table it is positive and commonly it increases with depth (Woessner & Poeter, 2024).

Chapter 3

Methods

3.1 Existing ADE solutions

The ADE (2.1) with time-dependent Boundary Conditions (BC) can in many cases be effectively solved with the use of the Laplace transform, especially when the domain is a semi-infinite homogeneous medium. For example, relatively simple closed-form solutions exist when the temperature at the inlet x_0 (the surface topography in our case) is either constant, or varies linearly or exponentially (Carslaw & Jaeger, 1959; Kurylyk et al., 2014). In order to accommodate for more complex surface temperature patterns, Kurylyk and Irvine, 2016 developed a solution for the case of piece-wise constant temperatures (a series of step changes) at the inlet x_0 . In a similar fashion, Mazaheri et al., 2013 developed a solution for the case of piece-wise linear temperatures at the inlet x_0 . Without the use of the Laplace transform, Stallman, 1965 developed a solution for the case of sinusoidal temperature changes at x_0 . For the case of a finite homogeneous layer, Davis, 1985 developed a Laplace transform solution for a constant temperature at the inlet x_0 . The main difference in this case is that the solution is given as an infinite sum, due to the inversion of the Laplace transform with the residue theorem.

When considering a heterogeneous medium, hinders the applicability of the Laplace transform, due to difficulties to compute its inverse back to the time domain. Carr, 2020 circumvented this difficulty by employing a numerical inversion of the Laplace transform, resulting in a semi-analytical solution. Rodrigo and Worthy, 2016 developed an analytical solution for the purely diffusion problem, by first reformulating the problem as a sequence of single layer problems subjected to arbitrary boundary conditions. The solutions obtained by Laplace transform were then inverted to the time domain, giving a system of renewal-type equations, which were finally solved by applying the Laplace transform. This solution procedure does not work by introducing advection into the system, as it results in a divergent sum when the flux continuity of two adjacent solutions is enforced. The problem with a divergent series can be avoided by not applying a Laplace transform for the second time; however this results in a Volterra integral equation of the 1st kind containing an infinite series of functions. Volterra equations of the first kind are, however, notoriously ill-posed (Guechi, 2024; Lamm, 2000), making this approach very unattractive from a mathematical standpoint.

By employing the General Integral Transform Technique instead of the Laplace transform, Pérez Guerrero et al., 2009 obtained a solution to the ADE (2.1) for the case of homogeneous BC in a finite, homogeneous 3D domain. Expanding this idea to a multi-layer case, C. Liu et al., 1997 developed a solution to the advection-diffusion-reaction equation by considering a pure diffusion auxiliary Eigenvalue Problem (EVP) which was then used in the integral transform. Although the pure diffusion EVP has many desirable properties (orthogonality, simplicity) it results in a coupled system of Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs). Jain, 2025; Jain et al., 2021; Pérez Guerrero et al., 2013 approached the same problem (although for a different set of BC and IC), by employing the Classical Integral Transform Technique (CITT) — i.e. instead of using the pure diffusion auxiliary EVP they used an advection-diffusion-reaction EVP. This allowed them to present the solution as an infinite system of decoupled ODEs, making it a very attractive solution procedure. However, the advection-diffusion-reaction EVP is non-self-adjoint, thus it misses many of the desirable properties of a self-adjoint EVP, one of which being orthogonality. To overcome this problem, the authors employed an integrating factor, thus introducing an additional yet crucial step into the solution procedure. Finally, while the authors considered very simple BC and IC, the solution procedure can be adjusted in order to accommodate more complex ones. For all the aforementioned reasons, the CITT approach was chosen for deriving the solution to Equation (2.1).

3.2 Mathematical formulation of the problem

Figure 3.1: Schematic representation of the problem

Consider a composite porous medium consisting of M parallel layers where the layer interfaces are at positions $0 = x_0 < x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_{M-1} < x_M$. For any layer, the governing ADE (2.1) can be rewritten as:

$$\frac{\partial T_m}{\partial t} = D_m \frac{\partial^2 T_m}{\partial x^2} - U_m \frac{\partial T_m}{\partial x} = L_m T_m; \quad \begin{array}{l} x_{m-1} < x < x_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots, M \end{array} \quad (3.1)$$

The following general Boundary Conditions (BC) are defined:

$$T_1 = v_0(t); \quad x = x_0 \quad (3.2a)$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} T_{m-1} = T_m \\ k_{m-1} \frac{dT_{m-1}}{dx} = k_m \frac{dT_m}{dx} \end{array} \right\} \quad \begin{array}{l} x = x_{m-1} \\ m = 2, 3, \dots, M \end{array} \quad (3.2b)$$

$$\alpha_M T_M + \alpha_M^* \frac{dT_M}{dx} = v_M(t); \quad x = x_M \quad (3.2c)$$

where $k_m \in \mathbb{R}$ is a generic coefficient preserving the flux continuity across the interfaces, which for the case of heat transport is equal to the thermal conductivity λ_m (Pérez Guerrero et al., 2013). The coefficients $\alpha_M, \alpha_M^* \in \mathbb{R}$ are introduced for generality and flexibility of the BC at the outlet (note that $\alpha_M = \alpha_M^* \neq 0$ must be satisfied). The general Initial Conditions (IC) are defined as:

$$T_m(x, t = 0) = F_m(x); \quad \begin{array}{l} x_{m-1} < x < x_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots, M \end{array} \quad (3.3)$$

The BC and IC are chosen in such a way that they describe the patterns observed in nature reasonably well, while still being simple enough in algebraic terms, to not make the solution procedure too complicated. Furthermore, the problem setup allows the IC to be defined separately in each layer. Our choice for the IC is to considered a piece-wise linear function, with one section per layer, i.e.:

$$F_m(x) = a_m + b_m x; \quad \begin{array}{l} x_{m-1} < x < x_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots, M \end{array} \quad (3.4)$$

where $a_m, b_m \in \mathbb{R}$. Similarly, $v_0(t)$ is also defined as a piece-wise linear function comprised of $J \in \mathbb{N}$ sections. Mathematically this can be written as:

$$v_0(t) = v_{0,0} + \sum_{j=1}^J \frac{\Delta v_{0,j}}{\Delta t_j} \left[(t - t_{j-1}) \mathbf{H}(t - t_{j-1}) - (t - t_j) \mathbf{H}(t - t_j) \right]; \quad \frac{\Delta v_{0,j}}{\Delta t_j} = \frac{v_{0,j} - v_{0,j-1}}{t_j - t_{j-1}} \quad (3.5)$$

where $\mathbf{H}(t)$ is the Heaviside step function, and $v_{0,j}$ is the surface temperature at time $t = t_j$ (conversely, $v_{0,0}$ is the surface temperature at time $t_0 = 0$). The temperature field on the outlet $v_M(t)$ is assumed to be constant with time, implying that

$$v_M(t) = \alpha_M F_M(x_M) + \alpha_M^* \left. \frac{dF_M}{dx} \right|_{x=x_M} \quad (3.6)$$

3.2.1 Non-dimensionalization

Equations (3.1 - 3.4) are non-dimensionalized to ensure generality of the results by introducing the following non-dimensional variables:

$$\tilde{x} = \frac{x}{x_M} \in [0, 1]; \quad \tilde{t} = \frac{U_M t}{x_M} \in \mathbb{R}; \quad \tilde{T}_m = \frac{T_m}{T_{\text{ref}}} \in \mathbb{R} \quad (3.7)$$

where $T_{\text{ref}}(\text{K})$ is an arbitrary reference temperature. By introducing these variables, the following non-dimensional coefficients appear in the ADE (3.1):

$$\tilde{D}_m = \frac{D_m}{U_M x_M} \in \mathbb{R}; \quad \tilde{U}_m = \frac{U_m}{U_M} \in \mathbb{R}; \quad \tilde{k}_m = \frac{k_m}{k_M} \in \mathbb{R} \quad (3.8)$$

leading to the following non-dimensional ADE:

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{T}_m}{\partial \tilde{t}} = \tilde{D}_m \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{T}_m}{\partial \tilde{x}^2} - \tilde{U}_m \frac{\partial \tilde{T}_m}{\partial \tilde{x}} = \tilde{L}_m \tilde{T}_m; \quad \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, M \quad (3.9)$$

Similarly, the general BC are redefined as:

$$\tilde{T}_1 = \tilde{v}_0(\tilde{t}); \quad \tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_0 \quad (3.10a)$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \tilde{T}_{m-1} = \tilde{T}_m \\ \tilde{k}_{m-1} \frac{d\tilde{T}_{m-1}}{d\tilde{x}} = \tilde{k}_m \frac{d\tilde{T}_m}{d\tilde{x}} \end{array} \right\} \quad \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_{m-1} \\ m = 2, 3, \dots, M \end{array} \quad (3.10b)$$

$$\tilde{\alpha}_M \tilde{T}_M + \tilde{\alpha}_M^* \frac{d\tilde{T}_M}{d\tilde{x}} = \tilde{v}_M(\tilde{t}); \quad \tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_M \quad (3.10c)$$

where $\tilde{\alpha}_M = \alpha_M$ and $\tilde{\alpha}_M^* = \alpha_M^*/x_M$.

The general IC are redefined as:

$$\tilde{T}_m(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t} = 0) = \tilde{F}_m(\tilde{x}); \quad \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, M \quad (3.11)$$

The specific IC (3.4) are redefined in non-dimensional terms as:

$$\tilde{F}_m(\tilde{x}) = \tilde{a}_m + \tilde{b}_m \tilde{x}; \quad \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, M \quad (3.12)$$

where:

$$\tilde{a}_m = \frac{a_m}{T_{\text{ref}}} \in \mathbb{R}; \quad \tilde{b}_m = \frac{b_m x_M}{T_{\text{ref}}} \in \mathbb{R} \quad (3.13)$$

Similarly, the specific BC on the inlet (3.5) are redefined as:

$$\tilde{v}_0(t) = \tilde{v}_{0,0} + \sum_{j=1}^J \frac{\Delta \tilde{v}_{0,j}}{\Delta \tilde{t}_j} \left[(\tilde{t} - \tilde{t}_{j-1}) \text{H}(\tilde{t} - \tilde{t}_{j-1}) - (\tilde{t} - \tilde{t}_j) \text{H}(\tilde{t} - \tilde{t}_j) \right]; \quad \frac{\Delta \tilde{v}_{0,j}}{\Delta \tilde{t}_j} = \frac{\tilde{v}_{0,j} - \tilde{v}_{0,j-1}}{\tilde{t}_j - \tilde{t}_{j-1}} \quad (3.14)$$

where:

$$\tilde{v}_{0,j} = \frac{v_{0,j}}{T_{\text{ref}}} \in \mathbb{R}; \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, J \quad (3.15)$$

Conversely the BC on the outlet (3.6) are redefined as:

$$\tilde{v}_M(t) = \tilde{\alpha}_M \tilde{F}_M(1) + \tilde{\alpha}_M^* \left. \frac{d\tilde{F}_M}{d\tilde{x}} \right|_{\tilde{x}=1} \quad (3.16)$$

3.3 Analytical solution via CITT

A solution to the problem (3.9 - 3.11) can be obtained by considering the superposition of three simpler problems (Hahn & Özişik, 2012):

$$\tilde{T}_m(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t}) = \Theta_m(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t}) + \Phi_m(\tilde{x})\tilde{v}_0(\tilde{t}) + \Gamma_m(\tilde{x})\tilde{v}_M(\tilde{t}); \quad \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots, M \end{array} \quad (3.17)$$

where:

- $\Phi_m(\tilde{x})$ for $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$ are the solutions of the steady-state problem with a single inhomogeneous BC at the inlet $\tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_0$. Mathematically the problem is formulated as:

$$\tilde{L}_m \Phi_m = 0; \quad \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots, M \end{array} \quad (3.18)$$

subject to the following BC:

$$\Phi_1 = 1; \quad \tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_0 \quad (3.19a)$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \Phi_{m-1} = \Phi_m \\ \tilde{k}_{m-1} \frac{d\Phi_{m-1}}{d\tilde{x}} = \tilde{k}_m \frac{d\Phi_m}{d\tilde{x}} \end{array} \right\} \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_{m-1} \\ m = 2, 3, \dots, M \end{array} \quad (3.19b)$$

$$\tilde{\alpha}_M \Phi_M + \tilde{\alpha}_M^* \frac{d\Phi_M}{d\tilde{x}} = 0; \quad \tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_M \quad (3.19c)$$

- $\Gamma_m(\tilde{x})$ for $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$ are the solutions of the steady-state problem with a single inhomogeneous BC at the outlet $\tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_M$. Mathematically the problem is formulated as:

$$\tilde{L}_m \Gamma_m = 0; \quad \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots, M \end{array} \quad (3.20)$$

subject to the following BC:

$$\Gamma_1 = 0; \quad \tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_0 \quad (3.21a)$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \Gamma_{m-1} = \Gamma_m \\ \tilde{k}_{m-1} \frac{d\Gamma_{m-1}}{d\tilde{x}} = \tilde{k}_m \frac{d\Gamma_m}{d\tilde{x}} \end{array} \right\} \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_{m-1} \\ m = 2, 3, \dots, M \end{array} \quad (3.21b)$$

$$\tilde{\alpha}_M \Gamma_M + \tilde{\alpha}_M^* \frac{d\Gamma_M}{d\tilde{x}} = 1; \quad \tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_M \quad (3.21c)$$

- $\Theta_m(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t})$ for $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$ are the solutions of the transient problem with homogeneous BC at both \tilde{x}_0 and \tilde{x}_M . Mathematically the problem is formulated as:

$$\frac{\partial \Theta_m}{\partial \tilde{t}} = \tilde{L}_m \Theta_m - S_m(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t}); \quad \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots, M \end{array} \quad (3.22)$$

where $S_m(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t})$ is the forcing term that naturally appears in the equation due the use of superposition (3.17):

$$S_m(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t}) = \Phi_m(\tilde{x}) \frac{d\tilde{v}_0(\tilde{t})}{d\tilde{t}} + \Gamma_m(\tilde{x}) \frac{d\tilde{v}_M(\tilde{t})}{d\tilde{t}}; \quad \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots, M \end{array} \quad (3.23)$$

The problem (3.22) is subject to the following homogeneous BC:

$$\Theta_1 = 0; \quad \tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_0 \quad (3.24a)$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \Theta_{m-1} = \Theta_m \\ \tilde{k}_{m-1} \frac{d\Theta_{m-1}}{d\tilde{x}} = \tilde{k}_m \frac{d\Theta_m}{d\tilde{x}} \end{array} \right\} \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_{m-1} \\ m = 2, 3, \dots, M \end{array} \quad (3.24b)$$

$$\tilde{\alpha}_M \Theta_M + \tilde{\alpha}_M^* \frac{d\Theta_M}{d\tilde{x}} = 0; \quad \tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_M \quad (3.24c)$$

and the following IC:

$$\Theta_m(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t} = 0) = \tilde{F}_m(\tilde{x}) - \Phi_m(\tilde{x})\tilde{v}_0(0) - \Gamma_m(\tilde{x})\tilde{v}_M(0); \quad \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots, M \end{array} \quad (3.25)$$

3.3.1 Solutions to $\Phi_m(\tilde{x})$

The general solution to (3.18) is given as:

$$\Phi_m(\tilde{x}) = \Phi_{A_m} \exp\left(\frac{\tilde{U}_m}{\tilde{D}_m} \tilde{x}\right) + \Phi_{B_m}; \quad \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots, M \end{array} \quad (3.26)$$

where $\Phi_{A_m}, \Phi_{B_m} \in \mathbb{R}$ are unknown coefficients that need to be determined from the BC (3.19). From the flux continuity condition in (3.19b) the following relationship is obtained:

$$\Phi_{A_m} = \Phi_{A_1} {}^A C_m; \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, M \quad (3.27)$$

where the coefficient ${}^A C_m$ is defined as:

$${}^A C_m = \frac{\tilde{U}_1 \tilde{k}_1}{\tilde{D}_1} \frac{\tilde{D}_m}{\tilde{U}_m \tilde{k}_m} \exp(s_m) \quad (3.28)$$

with:

$$s_m = \sum_{j=2}^m \left(\frac{\tilde{U}_{j-1}}{\tilde{D}_{j-1}} - \frac{\tilde{U}_j}{\tilde{D}_j} \right) \tilde{x}_{j-1} \quad (3.29)$$

From the temperature continuity condition (3.19b) the following relationship is obtained:

$$\Phi_{B_m} = \Phi_{A_1} {}^B C_m + \Phi_{B_1}; \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, M \quad (3.30)$$

where the constant ${}^B C_m$ is defined as:

$${}^B C_m = \frac{\tilde{U}_1 \tilde{k}_1}{\tilde{D}_1} \sum_{j=2}^m \left(\frac{\tilde{D}_{j-1}}{\tilde{k}_{j-1} \tilde{U}_{j-1}} - \frac{\tilde{D}_j}{\tilde{k}_j \tilde{U}_j} \right) \exp\left(s_{j-1} + \frac{\tilde{U}_{j-1}}{\tilde{D}_{j-1}} \tilde{x}_{j-1}\right) \quad (3.31)$$

The solutions to the problem (3.18 - 3.19) can thus be expressed as a linear combination of only two coefficients, namely Φ_{A_1} and Φ_{B_1} , which are finally obtained from the BC at the inlet (3.19a) and outlet (3.19c):

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{A_1} &= - \frac{\tilde{\alpha}_M \tilde{D}_M}{\tilde{\alpha}_M^* {}^A C_M \tilde{U}_M \exp\left(\frac{\tilde{U}_M}{\tilde{D}_M}\right) + \tilde{\alpha}_M \tilde{D}_M \left({}^A C_M \exp\left(\frac{\tilde{U}_M}{\tilde{D}_M}\right) + {}^B C_M - 1 \right)} \\ \Phi_{B_1} &= 1 - \Phi_{A_1} \end{aligned} \quad (3.32)$$

3.3.2 Solutions to $\Gamma_m(\tilde{x})$

Up until the definition of the coefficients Γ_{A_1} and Γ_{B_1} , the solution procedure is identical to the solution procedure for $\Phi_m(\tilde{x})$ provided in Section 3.3.1. The approach only differs in the last step, as the system must satisfy a different BC, i.e. (3.21a) and (3.21c) at the inlet and outlet respectively. This leads to the following definition of the coefficients in the first layer:

$$\begin{aligned}\Gamma_{A_1} &= \frac{\tilde{D}_M}{\tilde{\alpha}_M^* \text{AC}_M \tilde{U}_M \exp\left(\frac{\tilde{U}_M}{\tilde{D}_M}\right) + \tilde{\alpha}_M \tilde{D}_M \left(\text{AC}_M \exp\left(\frac{\tilde{U}_M}{\tilde{D}_M}\right) + \text{BC}_M - 1\right)} \\ \Gamma_{B_1} &= -\Gamma_{A_1}\end{aligned}\quad (3.33)$$

3.3.3 Solutions to $\Theta_m(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t})$

The general procedure for deriving a solution to the problem (3.22-3.25) can be summarized as follows:

- Define an auxiliary advection-dispersion EVP to the original problem $\Theta_m(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t})$ (3.22), satisfying the original BC (3.24) and find the associated eigenvalues λ_i and eigenfunctions $\psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x})$.
- Transform the EVP into a self-adjoint form by defining the integrating factor $\omega_m(\tilde{x})$ and define the orthogonality relation of the EVP
- Define the norm N_i and the integral transform pair - forward and inverse transform
- Find the general solution to the homogeneous part of the problem $\Theta_m^h(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t})$ by transforming the original problem into an infinite set of ODEs.
- Account for the inhomogeneous forcing term $S_m(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t})$ with the use of Duhamel's theorem.
- Implement the specific BC (3.14 - 3.16) and IC (3.12) into the solution

Auxiliary advection-dispersion EVP

This step is analogous to the separation of variables, where it is assumed that the problem (3.58) is a product of two functions, one of which is dependent purely on \tilde{x} and the other one purely on \tilde{t} . This leads to the following auxiliary advection-diffusion EVP (Pérez Guerrero et al., 2013):

$$\tilde{L}_m \psi_m + \lambda^2 \psi_m = 0 \quad \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots M \end{array} \quad (3.34)$$

which is subject to the following BC:

$$\psi_1 = 0 \quad \tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_0 \quad (3.35a)$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \psi_{m-1} = \psi_m \\ \tilde{k}_{m-1} \frac{d\psi_{m-1}}{d\tilde{x}} = \tilde{k}_m \frac{d\psi_m}{d\tilde{x}} \end{array} \right\} \quad \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_{m-1} \\ m = 2, 3, \dots M \end{array} \quad (3.35b)$$

$$\tilde{\alpha}_M \psi_M + \tilde{\alpha}_M^* \frac{d\psi_M}{d\tilde{x}} = 0 \quad \tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_M \quad (3.35c)$$

The EVP (3.34 - 3.35) has nontrivial solutions for a discrete set of eigenvalues $\lambda \equiv \lambda_i$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots \infty$ where the corresponding eigenfunctions are given as $\psi_m(\tilde{x}) \equiv \psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x})$. The general solution to the EVP (3.34) is given as (Pérez Guerrero et al., 2013):

$$\psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) = \Theta_{A,m,i} \nu_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) + \Theta_{B,m,i} \mu_{m,i}(\tilde{x}); \quad \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots M \\ i = 1, 2, \dots \infty \end{array} \quad (3.36)$$

where the functions $\nu_{m,i}(\tilde{x})$ and $\mu_{m,i}(\tilde{x})$ are given as:

$$\nu_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) = \exp\left(\frac{\tilde{U}_m}{2\tilde{D}_m}\tilde{x}\right) \sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}); \quad \mu_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) = \exp\left(\frac{\tilde{U}_m}{2\tilde{D}_m}\tilde{x}\right) \cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}) \quad (3.37)$$

The parameter $\beta_{m,i}$ represents the eigenvalue of the eigenfunction $\psi_{m,i}$ and is defined as:

$$\beta_{m,i} = \frac{\sqrt{4\lambda_i^2\tilde{D}_m - \tilde{U}_m^2}}{2\tilde{D}_m} \quad (3.38)$$

The unknown coefficients $\ominus A_{m,i}, \ominus B_{m,i} \in \mathbb{R}$ are determined from the BC (3.35). The value of $\ominus A_{1,i}$ is arbitrary (Pérez Guerrero et al., 2013) and is set to $\ominus A_{1,i} = 1$ which from (3.35a) directly leads to $\ominus B_{1,i} = 0$ for all $\lambda_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, \infty$. Using the interface conditions (3.35b), the coefficient in the next layer are obtained with the help of coefficient in the previous layer in a recursive manner as such:

$$\begin{aligned} \ominus A_{m,i} = & \ominus A_{m-1,i} \frac{\frac{\tilde{k}_{m-1}}{\tilde{k}_m} \mu_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \nu'_{m-1}(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) - \nu_{m-1}(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \mu'_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1})}{\mu_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \nu'_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) - \nu_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \mu'_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1})} \\ & + \ominus B_{m-1,i} \frac{\frac{\tilde{k}_{m-1}}{\tilde{k}_m} \mu_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \mu'_{m-1}(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) - \mu_{m-1}(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \mu'_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1})}{\mu_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \nu'_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) - \nu_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \mu'_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1})} \end{aligned} \quad (3.39a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \ominus B_{m,i} = & \ominus A_{m-1,i} \frac{\nu_{m-1}(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \nu'_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) - \frac{\tilde{k}_{m-1}}{\tilde{k}_m} \nu_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \nu'_{m-1}(\tilde{x}_{m-1})}{\mu_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \nu'_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) - \nu_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \mu'_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1})} \\ & + \ominus B_{m-1,i} \frac{\mu_{m-1}(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \nu'_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) - \frac{\tilde{k}_{m-1}}{\tilde{k}_m} \nu_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \mu'_{m-1}(\tilde{x}_{m-1})}{\mu_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \nu'_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) - \nu_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \mu'_m(\tilde{x}_{m-1})} \end{aligned} \quad (3.39b)$$

where the $(\cdot)'$ notation denotes the first derivative over \tilde{x} . Finally, the eigenvalues $\lambda_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, \infty$ are determined by finding the roots of the transcendental equation which is defined by the outlet BC (3.35c). Noting that $\tilde{x}_M = 1$, it is given as:

$$\tilde{\alpha}_M \left[\ominus A_{M,i} \nu_{M,i}(1) + \ominus B_{M,i} \mu_{M,i}(1) \right] + \tilde{\alpha}_M^* \left[\ominus A_{M,i} \nu'_{M,i}(1) + \ominus B_{M,i} \mu'_{M,i}(1) \right] = 0 \quad (3.40)$$

Integrating factor

The EVP (3.34-3.35) is non self-adjoint, meaning that the orthogonality of the eigenfunctions is not satisfied. Any linear second order differential operator can however be transformed into the self-adjoint Sturm-Liouville form (Herman, 2025). In context of the linear operator \tilde{L}_m , this enables the governing EVP (3.34) to be transformed into the desired Sturm-Liouville form and with that derive an orthogonality relation. For some generic function $f(\tilde{x})$, the Sturm-Liouville EVP is of the form (Herman, 2025):

$$\frac{d}{d\tilde{x}} \left[p(\tilde{x}) \frac{df(\tilde{x})}{d\tilde{x}} \right] + q(\tilde{x})f(\tilde{x}) + \lambda^2 w(\tilde{x})f(\tilde{x}) = 0 \quad (3.41)$$

In order to transform the EVP (3.34) into the desired form, both sides of the EVP are first multiplied by an unknown integrating factor $\omega_m(\tilde{x})$. This gives:

$$\omega_m(\tilde{x}) \tilde{D}_m \frac{d^2 \psi_{m,i}}{d\tilde{x}^2} - \omega_m(\tilde{x}) \tilde{U}_m \frac{d\psi_{m,i}}{d\tilde{x}} + \omega_m(\tilde{x}) \lambda_i^2 \psi_{m,i} = 0 \quad \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots, M \\ i = 1, 2, \dots, \infty \end{array} \quad (3.42)$$

When $\omega_m(\tilde{x})$ satisfies the following ODE:

$$\frac{d\omega_m(\tilde{x})}{d\tilde{x}} = -\frac{\tilde{U}_m}{\tilde{D}_m} \omega_m(\tilde{x}) \implies \omega_m(\tilde{x}) = \hat{\omega}_m \exp\left(-\frac{\tilde{U}_m}{\tilde{D}_m} \tilde{x}\right) \quad (3.43)$$

equation (3.42) reduces to the following Sturm-Liouville form:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{D}_m \frac{d}{d\tilde{x}} \left[\omega_m(\tilde{x}) \frac{d\psi_{m,i}}{d\tilde{x}} \right] + \omega_m(\tilde{x}) \lambda_i^2 \psi_{m,i} = 0 & \quad \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots, M & \\ i = 1, 2, \dots, \infty & \end{aligned} \quad (3.44)$$

The coefficient $\hat{\omega}_m$ in eq. (3.43) is a weight that is assigned to each integrating factor $\omega_m(\tilde{x})$ and is a key parameter in achieving orthogonality. As it turns out, when the weights are defined with the following sequence:

$$\hat{\omega}_m = \hat{\omega}_{m-1} \frac{\tilde{k}_m \tilde{D}_{m-1}}{\tilde{D}_m \tilde{k}_{m-1}} \exp \left(\left[\frac{\tilde{U}_m}{\tilde{D}_m} - \frac{\tilde{U}_{m-1}}{\tilde{D}_{m-1}} \right] \tilde{x}_{m-1} \right) \quad m = 2, 3, \dots, M \quad (3.45)$$

the EVP (3.34) is indeed orthogonal with respect to the integrating factor $\omega_m(\tilde{x})$ as proven in Section 3.3.3. The first weight in the sequence (3.45) is given as:

$$\hat{\omega}_1 = \exp \left(\frac{\tilde{U}_1}{\tilde{D}_1} \tilde{x}_1 \right) \quad (3.46)$$

Proof of orthogonality

In this section the notations $\omega_m \equiv \omega_m(\tilde{x})$ is used for sake of brevity. Consider two distinct eigenfunctions $\psi_{m,i}$ and $\psi_{m,j}$ where $i \neq j$. These eigenfunctions satisfy $\tilde{L}_m \psi_{m,i} + \lambda_i^2 \psi_{m,i} = 0$ and $\tilde{L}_m \psi_{m,j} + \lambda_j^2 \psi_{m,j} = 0$ by definition. Multiplying the two EVP with $\omega_m \psi_{m,j}$ and $\omega_m \psi_{m,i}$ respectively, yields the following two problems in Sturm-Liouville form:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{D}_m \frac{d}{d\tilde{x}} \left[\omega_m \frac{d\psi_{m,i}}{d\tilde{x}} \psi_{m,j} \right] &= -\omega_m \lambda_i^2 \psi_{m,i} \psi_{m,j} \\ \tilde{D}_m \frac{d}{d\tilde{x}} \left[\omega_m \frac{d\psi_{m,j}}{d\tilde{x}} \psi_{m,i} \right] &= -\omega_m \lambda_j^2 \psi_{m,j} \psi_{m,i} \end{aligned} \quad ; \quad \begin{aligned} \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots, M \end{aligned} \quad (3.47)$$

Subtracting one equation from the other gives:

$$\tilde{D}_m \frac{d}{d\tilde{x}} \left[\omega_m \left(\frac{d\psi_{m,i}}{d\tilde{x}} \psi_{m,j} - \frac{d\psi_{m,j}}{d\tilde{x}} \psi_{m,i} \right) \right] = -(\lambda_i^2 - \lambda_j^2) \omega_m \psi_{m,i} \psi_{m,j}; \quad \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, M \quad (3.48)$$

Upon integrating from $\tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_{m-1}$ to $\tilde{x} = \tilde{x}_m$, one obtains:

$$\tilde{D}_m \left[\omega_m \left(\frac{d\psi_{m,i}}{d\tilde{x}} \psi_{m,j} - \frac{d\psi_{m,j}}{d\tilde{x}} \psi_{m,i} \right) \right] \Big|_{\tilde{x}=\tilde{x}_{m-1}}^{\tilde{x}_m} = -(\lambda_i^2 - \lambda_j^2) \int_{\tilde{x}_{m-1}}^{\tilde{x}_m} \omega_m \psi_{m,i} \psi_{m,j} d\tilde{x}; \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, M \quad (3.49)$$

Summing over all layers $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$ yields the following sequence:

$$\begin{aligned} & \tilde{D}_M \left[\omega_M \left(\frac{d\psi_{M,i}}{d\tilde{x}} \psi_{M,j} - \frac{d\psi_{M,j}}{d\tilde{x}} \psi_{M,i} \right) \right]_{\tilde{x}=\tilde{x}_M=1} - \tilde{D}_1 \left[\omega_1 \left(\frac{d\psi_{1,i}}{d\tilde{x}} \psi_{1,j} - \frac{d\psi_{1,j}}{d\tilde{x}} \psi_{1,i} \right) \right]_{\tilde{x}=\tilde{x}_0=0} \\ & + \sum_{m=2}^M \left[\tilde{D}_{m-1} \omega_{m-1} \left(\frac{d\psi_{m-1,i}}{d\tilde{x}} \psi_{m-1,j} - \frac{d\psi_{m-1,j}}{d\tilde{x}} \psi_{m-1,i} \right) - \tilde{D}_m \omega_m \left(\frac{d\psi_{m,i}}{d\tilde{x}} \psi_{m,j} - \frac{d\psi_{m,j}}{d\tilde{x}} \psi_{m,i} \right) \right]_{\tilde{x}=\tilde{x}_{m-1}} \\ & = -(\lambda_i^2 - \lambda_j^2) \sum_{m=1}^M \int_{\tilde{x}_{m-1}}^{\tilde{x}_m} \omega_m \psi_{m,i} \psi_{m,j} d\tilde{x} \end{aligned} \quad (3.50)$$

From the inlet BC (3.35a) it holds that $\psi_{1,i}(0) = \psi_{1,j}(0) = 0$ making the second term on the left hand of eq. (3.50) to vanish. From the outlet BC (3.35c) it holds that:

$$\begin{cases} \psi_{M,i}(1) = \psi_{M,j}(1) = 0 & \tilde{\alpha}_M \neq 0 \wedge \tilde{\alpha}_M^* = 0 \\ \psi'_{M,i}(1) = \psi'_{M,j}(1) = 0 & \tilde{\alpha}_M = 0 \wedge \tilde{\alpha}_M^* \neq 0 \\ \psi'_{M,i}(1) = \frac{\tilde{\alpha}_M}{\tilde{\alpha}_M^*} \psi_{M,i}(1), \quad \psi'_{M,j}(1) = \frac{\tilde{\alpha}_M}{\tilde{\alpha}_M^*} \psi_{M,j}(1) & \tilde{\alpha}_M \neq 0 \wedge \tilde{\alpha}_M^* \neq 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.51)$$

In all three cases, the first term on the left-hand side of eq. (3.50) also vanishes. From the interface BC (3.35b) for any $m = 2, 3 \dots M$ it holds that $\psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) = \psi_{m-1,i}(\tilde{x}_{m-1})$ and $\psi'_{m,i}(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) = \frac{\tilde{k}_{m-1}}{\tilde{k}_m} \psi'_{m-1,i}(\tilde{x}_{m-1})$. The same holds in the case of the eigenfunctions corresponding to λ_j . Substituting these into the summation term on the left hand side of eq. (3.50) and using the definition of ω_m (3.43), one obtains:

$$\left(\tilde{D}_{m-1} \hat{\omega}_{m-1} e^{-\frac{\tilde{v}_{m-1}}{\tilde{D}_{m-1}} \tilde{x}_{m-1}} - \frac{\tilde{k}_{m-1}}{\tilde{k}_m} \tilde{D}_m \hat{\omega}_m e^{-\frac{\tilde{v}_m}{\tilde{D}_m} \tilde{x}_{m-1}} \right) \cdot \left[\left(\frac{d\psi_{m-1,i}}{d\tilde{x}} \psi_{m-1,j} - \frac{d\psi_{m-1,j}}{d\tilde{x}} \psi_{m-1,i} \right) \right]_{\tilde{x}=\tilde{x}_{m-1}} \quad (3.52)$$

Substituting the definitions of $\hat{\omega}_{m-1}$ and $\hat{\omega}_m$ in eq. (3.45) causes the terms in the round parenthesis to cancel out. Consequently, the entire third term on the left-hand side in eq. (3.50) vanishes. Finally, one is left with the following orthogonality relation:

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \int_{\tilde{x}_{m-1}}^{\tilde{x}_m} \omega_m \psi_{m,i} \psi_{m,j} d\tilde{x} = 0, \quad i \neq j \quad (3.53)$$

concluding the proof that the eigenfunctions $\psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x})$ and $\psi_{m,j}(\tilde{x})$ are indeed orthogonal with respect to the integrating factor $\omega_m(\tilde{x})$.

Norm and the integral transform pair

Firstly, the linear operators $\bar{\Gamma}_{m,i}$ is defined for sake of simplicity. When applied to an arbitrary function $f(\tilde{x})$, it results in:

$$\bar{\Gamma}_{m,i} f(\tilde{x}) = \int_{\tilde{x}_{m-1}}^{\tilde{x}_m} \omega_m(\tilde{x}) \psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) f(\tilde{x}) d\tilde{x} \quad \begin{array}{l} m = 1, 2, \dots M \\ i = 1, 2, \dots \infty \end{array} \quad (3.54)$$

The definition of the norm N_i follows directly from the orthogonality relation (3.53) and is given as:

$$N_i = \sum_{m=1}^M \bar{\Gamma}_{m,i} \psi_{m,i} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots \infty \quad (3.55)$$

Using the obtained norms, one can define for an arbitrary function $f(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t})$ the following forward integral transform:

$$\bar{f}_i(\tilde{t}) = \sum_{m=1}^M \bar{\Gamma}_{m,i} f(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t}); \quad i = 1, 2, \dots \infty \quad (3.56)$$

and the corresponding inverse transform:

$$f(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t}) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{\psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x})}{N_i} \bar{f}_i(\tilde{t}); \quad m = 1, 2, \dots M \quad (3.57)$$

Solution to $\Theta_m(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t})$

With the obtained integral transform pair (3.56 - 3.57), the homogeneous part of the original problem (3.22) can easily be solved as it allows for the PDE to be transformed into an infinite decoupled series of ODEs. The homogeneous part of the problem (3.22) is defined as:

$$\frac{\partial \Theta_m^h}{\partial \tilde{t}} = \tilde{L}_m \Theta_m^h; \quad \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots M \end{array} \quad (3.58)$$

and is satisfies the original BC (3.24) and IC (3.25). By first applying the inverse transform (3.57) and recalling the EVP (3.34) one obtains:

$$\frac{d}{d\tilde{t}} \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{\psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x})}{N_i} \overline{\Theta}_{h_i}(\tilde{t}) = - \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{\psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x})}{N_i} \overline{\Theta}_{h_i}(\tilde{t}) \lambda_i^2 \quad m = 1, 2, \dots M \quad (3.59)$$

Applying the forward transform (3.56) to both sides gives:

$$\frac{d}{d\tilde{t}} \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{\overline{\Theta}_{h_i}(\tilde{t})}{N_i} \sum_{m=1}^M \bar{I}_{m,i} \tilde{\psi}_{m,i} = - \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{\overline{\Theta}_{h_i}(\tilde{t})}{N_i} \lambda_i^2 \sum_{m=1}^M \bar{I}_{m,i} \tilde{\psi}_{m,i} \quad (3.60)$$

The orthogonality relation defined in (3.53) allows for the series to be solved in a decoupled manner, resulting in an infinite series of ODEs:

$$\frac{d\overline{\Theta}_{h_i}}{d\tilde{t}} + \overline{\Theta}_{h_i} \lambda_i^2 = 0 \implies \overline{\Theta}_{h_i}(\tilde{t}) = \overline{\Theta}_{h_i}(0) \exp(-\lambda_i^2 \tilde{t}) \quad i = 1, 2, \dots \infty \quad (3.61)$$

where $\overline{\Theta}_{h_i}(0)$ is the transformed IC (3.25). Using the notations $n \equiv m$ and $\tilde{x}' \equiv \tilde{x}$ to avoid confusion later on (\tilde{x}' indicates finite integration over \tilde{x} via operator $\bar{I}_{n,i}$) $\overline{\Theta}_{h_i}(0)$ is defined as:

$$\overline{\Theta}_{h_i}(0) = \sum_{n=1}^M \bar{I}_{n,i} \Theta_n(\tilde{x}', 0) \quad i = 1, 2, \dots \infty \quad (3.62)$$

By substituting (3.62) into (3.61) and applying the inverse integral transform (3.57) one obtains the following solution to the homogeneous part of (3.22):

$$\Theta_m^h(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t}) = \sum_{n=1}^M \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\lambda_i^2 \tilde{t}}}{N_i} \psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) \bar{I}_{n,i} \Theta_n(\tilde{x}', 0) \quad \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots M \end{array} \quad (3.63)$$

Finally, using the Duhamel's principle it is possible to account for the forcing term with the Duhamel's superposition integral (Hahn & Özişik, 2012). This leads to the following solution to the problem (3.22):

$$\Theta_m(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t}) = \sum_{n=1}^M \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\lambda_i^2 \tilde{t}}}{N_i} \psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) \bar{I}_{n,i} \Theta_n(\tilde{x}', 0) - \int_{\tau=0}^{\tilde{t}} \frac{e^{-\lambda_i^2 (\tilde{t}-\tau)}}{N_i} \psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) \bar{I}_{n,i} S_n(\tilde{x}', \tau) d\tau \quad \begin{array}{l} \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \\ m = 1, 2, \dots M \end{array} \quad (3.64)$$

Noting the definitions of the $\Theta_n(\tilde{x}, 0)$ in eq. (3.25), $\tilde{v}_M(\tilde{t})$ in eq. (3.24c) and $S_n(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t})$ in eq. (3.23), the separate elements in eq. (3.64) can be further broken down to the following elementary components:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{I}_{n,i} \Theta_n(\tilde{x}, 0) &= \bar{I}_{n,i} \tilde{F}_n(\tilde{x}) - \bar{I}_{n,i} \Phi_n(\tilde{x}) \tilde{v}_0(0) - \bar{I}_{n,i} \Gamma_n(\tilde{x}) \tilde{v}_M(0) & m = 1, 2, \dots M \\ \bar{I}_{n,i} S_n(\tilde{x}, \tau) &= \frac{d\tilde{v}_0(\tau)}{d\tau} \bar{I}_{n,i} \Phi_n & i = 1, 2, \dots \infty \end{aligned} \quad (3.65)$$

Furthermore, recalling the definition of $\tilde{v}_0(\tau)$ (3.14) it holds that:

$$\frac{d\tilde{v}_0(\tau)}{d\tau} = \frac{\Delta \tilde{v}_{0,j}}{\Delta \tilde{t}_j}, \quad \tilde{t}_{j-1} \leq \tau \leq \tilde{t}_j \quad j = 1, 2, \dots J \quad (3.66)$$

with the discontinuities occurring at the times $\tilde{t} = \tilde{t}_1, \tilde{t}_2, \dots \tilde{t}_J$. Then the second term in the general solution (3.64) can for any $m = 1, 2, \dots M$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots \infty$ and for $\tilde{t}_J \leq \tilde{t}$ be broken into separate parts on the discontinuities (Hahn & Özişik, 2012), resulting in the following expression:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\tau=0}^{\tilde{t}} \frac{e^{-\lambda_i^2 (\tilde{t}-\tau)}}{N_i} \psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) \bar{I}_{n,i} S_n(\tilde{x}', \tau) d\tau \\ &= \frac{\bar{I}_{n,i} \Phi_n \psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x})}{N_i} \left[\sum_{j=1}^J \frac{\Delta \tilde{v}_{0,j}}{\Delta \tilde{t}_j} \int_{\tau=\tilde{t}_{j-1}}^{\tilde{t}_j} e^{-\lambda_i^2 (\tilde{t}-\tau)} d\tau + \frac{\Delta \tilde{v}_{0,J}}{\Delta \tilde{t}_J} \int_{\tau=\tilde{t}_J}^{\tilde{t}} e^{-\lambda_i^2 (\tilde{t}-\tau)} d\tau \right] \\ &= \frac{\bar{I}_{n,i} \Phi_n \psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x})}{\lambda_i^2 N_i} \left[\sum_{j=1}^J \frac{\Delta \tilde{v}_{0,j}}{\Delta \tilde{t}_j} \left(e^{-\lambda_i^2 (\tilde{t}-\tilde{t}_j)} - e^{-\lambda_i^2 (\tilde{t}-\tilde{t}_{j-1})} \right) + \frac{\Delta \tilde{v}_{0,J}}{\Delta \tilde{t}_J} \left(1 - e^{-\lambda_i^2 (\tilde{t}-\tilde{t}_J)} \right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (3.67)$$

On a final note, it is worth mentioning that by rearranging the terms in eq. (3.64) one can obtain the composite medium Green's function $G_{m,n}(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t}|\tilde{x}', \tau)$ similar to the one provided by Hahn and Özişik, 2012 for the case of multi-layer diffusion.

Closed form solution to $\Theta_m(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t})$

The solution (3.64) is expressible in a closed form equation. The coefficients ${}^{\Theta}A_{m,i}$ (3.39a) and ${}^{\Theta}B_{m,i}$ (3.39b) are given respectively as:

$$\begin{aligned}
{}^{\Theta}A_{m,i} &= [A1_{m,i} + A2_{m,i}] \exp\left(\left[\frac{\tilde{U}_{m-1}}{2\tilde{D}_{m-1}} - \frac{\tilde{U}_m}{2\tilde{D}_m}\right]\tilde{x}_{m-1}\right) \\
A1_{m,i} &= {}^{\Theta}A_{m-1,i} \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \sin(\beta_{m-1,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \\ &+ \frac{\cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1})}{\beta_{m,i}\tilde{k}_m} \left[\left(\frac{\tilde{U}_{m-1}\tilde{k}_{m-1}}{2\tilde{D}_{m-1}} - \frac{\tilde{U}_m\tilde{k}_m}{2\tilde{D}_m}\right) \sin(\beta_{m-1,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1}) + \beta_{m-1,i}\tilde{k}_{m-1} \cos(\beta_{m-1,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \right] \end{aligned} \right\} \\
A2_{m,i} &= {}^{\Theta}B_{m-1,i} \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \cos(\beta_{m-1,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \\ &+ \frac{\cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1})}{\beta_{m,i}\tilde{k}_m} \left[\left(\frac{\tilde{U}_{m-1}\tilde{k}_{m-1}}{2\tilde{D}_{m-1}} - \frac{\tilde{U}_m\tilde{k}_m}{2\tilde{D}_m}\right) \cos(\beta_{m-1,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1}) - \beta_{m-1,i}\tilde{k}_{m-1} \sin(\beta_{m-1,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \right] \end{aligned} \right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{3.68}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
{}^{\Theta}B_{m,i} &= [B1_{m,i} + B2_{m,i}] \exp\left(\left[\frac{\tilde{U}_{m-1}}{2\tilde{D}_{m-1}} - \frac{\tilde{U}_m}{2\tilde{D}_m}\right]\tilde{x}_{m-1}\right) \\
B1_{m,i} &= {}^{\Theta}A_{m-1,i} \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \sin(\beta_{m-1,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \\ &+ \frac{\sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1})}{\beta_{m,i}\tilde{k}_m} \left[\left(\frac{\tilde{U}_m\tilde{k}_m}{2\tilde{D}_m} - \frac{\tilde{U}_{m-1}\tilde{k}_{m-1}}{2\tilde{D}_{m-1}}\right) \sin(\beta_{m-1,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1}) - \beta_{m-1,i}\tilde{k}_{m-1} \cos(\beta_{m-1,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \right] \end{aligned} \right\} \\
B2_{m,i} &= {}^{\Theta}B_{m-1,i} \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \cos(\beta_{m-1,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \\ &+ \frac{\sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1})}{\beta_{m,i}\tilde{k}_m} \left[\left(\frac{\tilde{U}_m\tilde{k}_m}{2\tilde{D}_m} - \frac{\tilde{U}_{m-1}\tilde{k}_{m-1}}{2\tilde{D}_{m-1}}\right) \cos(\beta_{m-1,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1}) + \beta_{m-1,i}\tilde{k}_{m-1} \sin(\beta_{m-1,i}\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \right] \end{aligned} \right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{3.69}$$

Next, the transcendental equation (3.40) admits to the following closed form:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\left. \begin{aligned} &{}^{\Theta}A_{M,i} \left[\tilde{\alpha}_M \sin(\beta_{M,i}) + \tilde{\alpha}_M^* \left(\frac{\tilde{U}_M}{2\tilde{D}_M} \sin(\beta_{M,i}) + \beta_{M,i} \cos(\beta_{M,i}) \right) \right] \\ &+ {}^{\Theta}B_{M,i} \left[\tilde{\alpha}_M \cos(\beta_{M,i}) + \tilde{\alpha}_M^* \left(\frac{\tilde{U}_M}{2\tilde{D}_M} \cos(\beta_{M,i}) - \beta_{M,i} \sin(\beta_{M,i}) \right) \right] \end{aligned} \right\} = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{3.70}$$

The closed form of (3.64) is obtainable by considering only the separate components inside the summation series — namely $\bar{I}_{n,i}\Theta_n(\tilde{x}, 0)$ and $\bar{I}_{n,i}S_n(\tilde{x}, \tau)$ and the norm N_i . Since these are all defined in terms of the linear operator $\bar{I}_{m,i}$, it is sufficient to present only the closed form equations in terms of the indefinite integral operator $I_{m,i}$ which when applied to an arbitrary function $f(\tilde{x})$ is defined as:

$$I_{m,i}f(\tilde{x}) = \int \omega_m(\tilde{x})\psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x})f(\tilde{x})d\tilde{x} \quad \implies \quad \bar{I}_{m,i}f(\tilde{x}) = I_{m,i}f(\tilde{x}_m) - I_{m,i}f(\tilde{x}_{m-1}) \quad \begin{array}{l} m = 1, 2, \dots, M \\ i = 1, 2, \dots, \infty \end{array} \tag{3.71}$$

The closed form equation of the norm N_i can thus be defined solely in terms of $I_{m,i}\psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x})$ (see eq. 3.55). It is given as:

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{m,i}\psi_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) &= \frac{\hat{\omega}_m}{4\beta_{m,i}} [N1_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) + N2_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) + N3_{m,i}(\tilde{x})] \\
N1_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) &= \ominus A_{m,i}^2 [2\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x} - \sin(2\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x})] \\
N2_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) &= \ominus B_{m,i}^2 [2\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x} + \sin(2\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x})] \\
N3_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) &= 4\ominus A_{m,i}\ominus B_{m,i}\sin^2(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x})
\end{aligned} \tag{3.72}$$

Similarly, the closed form equations of $\bar{I}_{n,i}\Theta_n(\tilde{x}, 0)$ and $\bar{I}_{n,i}S_n(\tilde{x}, \tau)$ can both defined solely in terms of $I_{m,i}\Phi_m(\tilde{x})$, $I_{m,i}\Gamma_m(\tilde{x})$ and $I_{n,i}F_n(\tilde{x})$ (see eq. 3.65). The closed form of $I_{m,i}\Phi_m(\tilde{x})$ is given as:

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{m,i}\Phi_m(\tilde{x}) &= \frac{2\hat{\omega}_m\tilde{D}_m}{4\tilde{D}_m^2\beta_{m,i}^2 + \tilde{U}_m^2} \begin{cases} \Phi A_m [\Phi 1_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) + \Phi 2_{m,i}(\tilde{x})] e^{\frac{\tilde{U}_m}{2\tilde{D}_m}\tilde{x}} & \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \\ + \Phi B_m [\Phi 3_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) - \Phi 4_{m,i}(\tilde{x})] e^{-\frac{\tilde{U}_m}{2\tilde{D}_m}\tilde{x}} & m = 1, 2, \dots M \\ & i = 1, 2, \dots \infty \end{cases} \\
\Phi 1_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) &= \ominus B_{m,i} [2\tilde{D}_m\beta_{m,i}\sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}) + \tilde{U}_m\cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x})] \\
\Phi 2_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) &= \ominus A_{m,i} [\tilde{U}_m\sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}) - 2\tilde{D}_m\beta_{m,i}\cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x})] \\
\Phi 3_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) &= \ominus B_{m,i} [2\tilde{D}_m\beta_{m,i}\sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}) - \tilde{U}_m\cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x})] \\
\Phi 4_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) &= \ominus A_{m,i} [\tilde{U}_m\sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}) + 2\tilde{D}_m\beta_{m,i}\cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x})]
\end{aligned} \tag{3.73}$$

Note that since the general form of the solution to $\Gamma_n(\tilde{x})$ is essentially the same as for $\Phi_n(\tilde{x})$, then also the equation for $I_{m,i}\Gamma_m(\tilde{x})$ takes upon the same form as (3.73), with the difference occurring in the coefficients, i.e. the coefficients ΦA_m and ΦB_m in eq. (3.73) are substituted for ΓA_m and ΓB_m respectively. The expression for $I_{n,i}F_n(\tilde{x})$ is given as:

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{m,i}\tilde{F}_m(\tilde{x}) &= \frac{2\tilde{D}_m\hat{\omega}_m \exp\left(-\frac{\tilde{U}_m}{2\tilde{D}_m}\tilde{x}\right)}{4\tilde{D}_m^2\beta_{m,i}^2 + \tilde{U}_m^2} \begin{cases} \tilde{a}_m [\tilde{F}1_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) - \tilde{F}2_{m,i}(\tilde{x})] & \tilde{x}_{m-1} < \tilde{x} < \tilde{x}_m \\ + \frac{\tilde{b}_m}{4\tilde{D}_m^2\beta_{m,i}^2 + \tilde{U}_m^2} [\tilde{F}3_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) - \tilde{F}4_{m,i}(\tilde{x})] & m = 1, 2, \dots M \\ & i = 1, 2, \dots \infty \end{cases} \\
\tilde{F}1_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) &= \ominus B_{m,i} [2\tilde{D}_m\beta_{m,i}\sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}) - \tilde{U}_m\cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x})] \\
\tilde{F}2_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) &= \ominus A_{m,i} [2\tilde{D}_m\beta_{m,i}\cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}) + \tilde{U}_m\sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x})] \\
\tilde{F}3_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) &= \ominus B_{m,i} \begin{cases} 8\tilde{D}_m^3\beta_{m,i}^2 [\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}\sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}) + \cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x})] \\ + 4\tilde{D}_m^2\tilde{U}_m\beta_{m,i} [2\sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}) - \beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}\cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x})] \\ + 2\tilde{D}_m\tilde{U}_m^2 [\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}\sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}) - \cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x})] \\ - \tilde{U}_m^3\tilde{x}\cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}) \end{cases} \\
\tilde{F}4_{m,i}(\tilde{x}) &= \ominus A_{m,i} \begin{cases} 8\tilde{D}_m^3\beta_{m,i}^2 [\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}\cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}) - \sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x})] \\ + 4\tilde{D}_m^2\tilde{U}_m\beta_{m,i} [2\cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}) + \beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}\sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x})] \\ + 2\tilde{D}_m\tilde{U}_m^2 [\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}\cos(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}) + \sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x})] \\ + \tilde{U}_m^3\tilde{x}\sin(\beta_{m,i}\tilde{x}) \end{cases}
\end{aligned} \tag{3.74}$$

3.3.4 Validation

The accuracy of the solution was assessed by considering a $M = 10$ layer setup with $\tilde{x}_0 = 0$, $\tilde{x}_M = 1$ and the layer interfaces located at

$$x_m \in \{0.14, 0.16, 0.22, 0.26, 0.62, 0.72, 0.83, 0.86, 0.87\}, \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, 9 \quad (3.75)$$

The parameters are homogeneous across all layers $\tilde{D}_m = 0.24$, $\tilde{U}_m = 1$, $\tilde{k}_m = 1$; $m = 1, 2 \dots M$. Furthermore zero IC $\tilde{T}_m(\tilde{x}, 0) = 0$, $m = 1, 2 \dots M$ were assumed with Dirichlet BC on both ends, where the temperature at the inlet is linearly increasing and zero temperature at the outlet:

$$\tilde{T}_0(0, \tilde{t}) = \tilde{v}_0(\tilde{t}) = \tilde{p}_0 + \tilde{p}_1 \tilde{t}; \quad \tilde{T}_M(1, \tilde{t}) = \tilde{v}_M(\tilde{t}) = 0 \quad (3.76)$$

implying $\tilde{\alpha}_M = 1$ and $\tilde{\alpha}_M^* = 0$. The non-dimensional parameters \tilde{p}_0 and \tilde{p}_1 are analogous to $\tilde{v}_{0,0}$ and $\Delta \tilde{v}_{0,j} / \Delta \tilde{t}_j$ in eq. (3.14). The closed form solution to this problem can be obtained with the help of the Laplace transform as derived in Appendix A. As observed in Figure 3.2, the steady state solutions clearly satisfy the prescribed boundary conditions and are in line with the steady state solution $\tilde{\Phi}(\tilde{x})$ (see eq. A.19). As can be observed in Figure 3.2, the orthogonality was confirmed by numerically computing the integral in eq. (3.53).

Figure 3.2: A) Plot of the orthogonality relation for the norm N_i for the first 50 eigenvalues and B) plot of steady state solutions $\Phi(\tilde{x})$ and $\Gamma(\tilde{x})$ in a composite medium in reference to the steady state solution $\tilde{\Phi}(\tilde{x})$ in a homogeneous medium. The gray vertical lines in B) represent the interfaces \tilde{x}_m , $m = 1, 2 \dots 9$.

Finally, a representative case of the inlet BC was assumed by setting $\tilde{p}_0 = 1$ and $\tilde{p}_1 = 1$, meaning that the temperature at the inlet is initially $\tilde{v}_0(0) = 1$ and at $\tilde{t} = 1$ it increases to $\tilde{v}_0(1) = 2$. As observed in Figure 3.3, the obtained CITT solution clearly satisfies this condition, while being in very good agreement with the Laplace transform solution (A.18).

The governing ADE (2.1) is a parabolic PDE and as such the maximum principle applies (Jain et al., 2021). In accordance, the maximum truncation error of the solution is expected to develop along the spatial boundary at initial time (Jain et al., 2021). As expected, the RMSE between the two solutions is the greatest as $\tilde{t} \rightarrow 0$ and on the flip side, as the number of summations i increases, the RMSE decreases by orders of magnitude. For $i = 1$, RMSE varies from 0.6 to 0.06 as \tilde{t} ranges from $10E-04$ to 1. For $i = 5$, this range tightens to $[0.25, 2.0E-03]$, and for $i = 20$, it contracts further to $[8.0E-02, 7.0E-05]$. This behaviour of the RMSE is portrayed in Figure 3.3. Similarly, the series summations of the transformed solution components in eq. (3.65), namely $\tilde{I}_{m,i} \Phi_m$, $\tilde{I}_{m,i} \Gamma_m$, $\tilde{I}_{m,i} \tilde{F}_m$ converge rapidly, needing only about 15 to 20 terms to give satisfactory results as can be observed in Figure 3.4

Van Genuchten and Alves, 1982 have noted that the series solution to the single layer ADE (2.1) converge slowly for the case of large Peclet numbers $Pe = \frac{Ud}{D}$, where d is the layer thickness. In this setup, the obtained solution (3.64) requires an increasing amount of summations when $Pe = \frac{\tilde{U}_m}{\tilde{D}_m} \approx 37.5$ (see Figure 3.5), while displaying nonphysical behaviour when $Pe \gtrsim 37.5$. This indicates that a different approach is better suited to obtain a solution at larger Pe (see Section 5.2).

Finally it is noted, that increasing the number of layers or partitioning the domain into layers of various thicknesses $\tilde{d}_m = \tilde{x}_m - \tilde{x}_{m-1}$ does not change the RMSE behaviour (see Figure 3.6). While this adds to the computational cost, it is however useful, as it implies that the domain can be partitioned in any way necessary, without increasing the error.

Figure 3.3: A) comparison between the Laplace and CITT distribution of $\tilde{T}_m(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t})$ at different times in the range $\tilde{t} \in [10^{-4}, 1]$ for $i \in \{5, 25, 50\}$ series summations and B) RMSE estimates between Laplace and CITT solutions for $i \in [1, 50]$ series summations in respect to \tilde{t} . The gray vertical lines in A) represent the interfaces \tilde{x}_m , $m = 1, 2, \dots, 9$.

Figure 3.4: Values of N_i and the sums of main solution components $\bar{I}_{m,i} \Phi_m$, $\bar{I}_{m,i} \Gamma_m$, $\bar{I}_{m,i} \tilde{F}_m$ in respect to the number of terms summed i .

Figure 3.5: Convergence of the CITT solution when $Pe = 37.5$ for different terms summed $i \in \{50, 75, 100, 250\}$ at two different \tilde{t} increments.

Figure 3.6: A) RMSE over \tilde{t} in respect to the number of layers M in an equidistant setup ($\tilde{d}_m = \text{const.}$) and B) RMSE over \tilde{t} in respect to the varying layer thicknesses \tilde{d}_m for $M = 100$. For the case of $\text{std}(\tilde{d}_m) \rightarrow 0$ then $\tilde{d}_m \rightarrow \text{const.}$ and vice versa. For example, when $\text{std}(\tilde{d}_m) \approx 8.9E - 03$ then $\min(\tilde{d}_m) \approx 4E - 06$ and $\max(\tilde{d}_m) \approx 3E - 02$

Chapter 4

Application to the Area of Study

4.1 Workflow

The specific problem setup for each of the GWT monitoring stations can be described as:

- According to geographical location, each GWT monitoring point is assigned a corresponding surface location unit. The surface is partitioned according to:
 - Topographical units, where each unit is assigned a dh/dx value calculated with the help of the GW table records (see Section 4.2.2). This (in conjunction with the soil parameters) allows q and consequently U_m to be determined (see Section 4.2.3).
 - UHI units, done in two distinct approaches - according to area type and according to surface imperviousness levels. Each UHI unit is assigned a historical GST record, which is a combination of GST (measured and derived) and AST records (see Section 4.2.4). The obtained GST records are then used as inlet BC (3.5).
- With the help of the vertical geological profiles, the subsurface is partitioned into layers of distinct soil types. Each layer is then assigned all parameters specific to the corresponding soil type, allowing for the determination of D_m (and U_m) values (see Section 4.2.1).
- Finally, for each GWT monitoring point, the IC and outlet BC are determined from the oldest existing GWT profile (see eq. 3.4 and eq. 3.2c)

A schematic representation of the workflow is shown in Figure 4.1. The considered GWT points with the relevant information are presented in Table 4.1. For all the presented results, C_w was set to $4.18 \text{ MJ K}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-3}$.

Figure 4.1: Schematic representation of the simulation workflow

GWT point	z (m)	z_{GWT} (m)	\bar{z}_{GW} (m)	Start	Topo. Unit	Area Type	Surf. Imper.
6125	100	100.00	12.21	1978	BP	G	1
6078 ¹	127	124.42	15.22	1979	BP	R	4
6511	77	74.40	4.06	1997	PV	G	1
8200 ¹	91	61.50	1.23	1993	PV	G	1
8215	107	105.00	-0.29	1993	PV	G	1
5097	100	89.41	9.09	1997	PV	C	4
7040	185	175.00	12.24	1990	TP	R	1
7043 ¹	189	195.32	3.27	1990	TP	G	1
7056	199	195.67	30.95	1990	TP	G	1
8055 ¹	132	124.63	5.63	1993	WBS	G	1
7030	141	102.00	4.06	1984	WBS	C	2
8061 ¹	231	104.40	2.86	1993	WBS	C	2
6007	132	132.00	4.78	1979	WBS	C	3
6022	145	138.52	5.50	1979	WBS	C	5
7007 ¹	96	88.59	2.98	1984	WBS	C	5
6039 ¹	155	147.45	5.99	1979	WBS	R	5

Table 4.1: GWT monitoring stations used in this study with the corresponding borehole z and maximum depth of measured GWT z_{GWT} , multi-annual mean groundwater table depth \bar{z}_{GW} , beginning of measurements, topographical unit (BP: Barnim Plateau, PV: Panke Valley, TP: Teltow Plateau, WBS: Warsaw-Berlin Spillway; see Section 4.2.2), surface area partition unit by area type (G: green area, R: residential area, C: commercial area; see Section 4.2.4) and surface area partition unit by surface impermeousness (1: $< 20\%$, 2: $20 - 40\%$, 3: $40 - 60\%$, 4: $60 - 80\%$, 5: $> 80\%$; see Section 4.2.4) respectively. The standard deviation from the mean GW table is on average approximately 0.5 m for all GWT points, or at most 1.2 m. ¹ No groundwater table data was available and the data from the nearest available piezometer was used.

4.2 Parameter estimation

4.2.1 Soil properties

For the majority of the soil types present within the study area, extensive laboratory tests were carried out by Hörmann and Birner, 2018 to assess the bulk thermal conductivity λ_b . As a result from the study, each soil type is paired with a recommended value of λ_b , which was adopted in this study. The λ_b for lignite and peat were taken from Verein Deutscher Ingenieure (VDI), 2010 where they are provided as the industry standard. For the anthropogenic material (rubble, municipal solid waste etc.), an estimate of λ_b in saturated conditions was taken from Senate Department for the Environment, 2018.

To the best of the author’s knowledge, no laboratory study on the bulk volumetric heat capacities C_b exists for the soil types as applicable to the study area. As such, the values of C_b in saturated conditions were taken from Senate Department for the Environment, 2018; Verein Deutscher Ingenieure (VDI), 2010, where they are again provided as industry standard.

Lastly, hydraulic conductivities K were adopted from Hörmann and Birner, 2018 where the soils are assigned a conductivity class on a logarithmic scale, providing K within an expected range. The values of K that were adopted, are given as the orders of magnitude of their arithmetic mean. The two exceptions are lignite and loam, for which K was taken from Manhenke et al., 2001, where they are given as the regional estimates for north and middle Germany.

For the soil types that could not be found in the aforementioned sources, parameters of the most similar soil type were adopted. In total, 17 major soil types were recognised for the 16 GWT monitoring points considered in this study (see Table 4.2).

Lastly, an additional 8 mixed soil types were recognised, containing a combination of the aforementioned 17 ones. The parameters for these mixed soils were determined by calculating the arithmetic mean of the corresponding parameters of their constituent soil types.

Unit	Name	λ_b ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	C_b ($\text{MJ m}^{-3} \text{K}$)	K (m s^{-1})
Quaternary	Anthropogenic Material ^{2,2,1}	1.6	2.5	$1E-09$
	Stones ^{5,5,1}	3.0	2.4	$1E-04$
	Gravel ^{1,2,1}	3.0	2.4	$1E-04$
	Coarse Sand ^{1,5,1}	3.0	2.4	$1E-04$
	Sand ^{1,2,1}	3.0	2.5	$1E-04$
	Fine Sand ^{1,5,1}	2.7	2.5	$1E-04$
	Till ^{1,2,1}	3.0	2.0	$1E-07$
	Carbonate Till ^{5,5,5}	3.0	2.0	$1E-07$
	Loam ^{5,5,4}	2.0	2.4	$1E-09$
	Silt ^{1,2,1}	2.0	2.4	$1E-09$
	Silty Mud ^{5,5,5}	1.8	2.4	$1E-09$
	Clay ^{1,2,1}	1.8	2.4	$1E-09$
	Peat ^{3,2,1}	0.4	0.8	$1E-09$
	Lignite ^{3,2,4}	0.4	0.8	$1E-09$
Tertiary	Rupelian Clay ^{1,5,1}	1.4	2.4	$1E-09$

Table 4.2: Parameter values for the soils found within the area of study. The superscripts in the "Name" column indicate the source of the values for λ_b , C_b and K class respectively (¹ Hörmann and Birner, 2018, ² Senate Department for the Environment, 2018, ³ Verein Deutscher Ingenieure (VDI), 2010, ⁴ Manhenke et al., 2001, ⁵ taken from another soil type).

4.2.2 Vertical hydraulic gradients

Assuming two adjacent piezometers labeled as A and B, the vertical hydraulic gradient in the saturated zone was estimated as (Woessner & Poeter, 2024):

$$\frac{dh}{dx} \approx \frac{\Delta h}{\Delta L} = \frac{|h_B - h_A|}{|z_B - z_A|} \quad (4.1)$$

where $\Delta h(\text{m})$ is the absolute head difference between the two piezometers and $\Delta L(\text{m})$ is the vertical distance separating the two measurement locations (depth of the piezometer / piezometer filter; see Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.2: Schematic representation of the estimation of the vertical hydraulic gradient in the saturated zone. The groundwater flows downward in the piezometer with the higher head (piezometer A) and upwards with the same magnitude in the piezometer with the lower head (piezometer B).

Within the area of study a total of 68 piezometers pairs were selected, which are located within a radius of 1 to 5 m of one another (see Table 4.3). With the obtained pairs an estimate of the vertical hydraulic gradients for each of the main topographic units was calculated, namely the Barnim plateau, Teltow plateau, Nauen plate, Panke valley and Warsaw-Berlin spillway (see Figure 4.3).

Figure 4.3: Vertical hydraulic gradient trends on a multi-annual timescale (top) and a seasonal timescale (bottom) for the main topographical units. The seasonal variability is presented as variation around the mean annual temperature. Note that only the years with measurements taken in all 12 months and more than 4 piezometer pairs per topographical unit are taken into consideration.

Topographical Unit	Piezometer Pairs	GW Temp.	$\Delta h/\Delta L(\text{m m}^{-1})$
Barnim Plateau	16	2	$9.43E - 02$
Nauen Plate	4	0	$9.44E - 03$
Panke Valley	23	4	$3.0E - 02$
Teltow Plateau	12	3	$8.91E - 03$
Warsaw-Berlin Spillway	13	7	$6.88E - 03$

Table 4.3: Number of piezometer pairs, number of GW temperature monitoring stations and estimates of the mean vertical hydraulic gradients per topographical unit

A higher $\Delta h/\Delta L$ variability can be observed on the Barnim plateau and in the Panke valley, while the other units display more consistent estimates. This can likely be attributed to a higher difference in the groundwater table depth within these two units. The multi-annual trend on the Barnim plateau displays a substantial change in hydraulic gradients over the years, which can in part be explained by the increased occurrence of drought years in the last decade. However, hardly any variation in the gradients on a seasonal level can be observed on all topographical units.

4.2.3 Vertical hydraulic flux

In the saturated zone all the available pore spaces are filled with groundwater. In order to preserve mass balance the volumetric inflow of groundwater into a REV must be equal to the volumetric outflow (Woessner & Poeter, 2024). Expanding this idea to the horizontally stratified porous medium depicted in Figure 1.6 where groundwater flow q is perpendicular to the soil layers, results in q being constant along the entire soil column (Woessner & Poeter, 2024). Combined with the fact that hydraulic conductivity values K differ from layer to layer, leads to the vertical hydraulic gradient being different in each layer (Woessner & Poeter, 2024). Darcy's law (2.6) in this setup can thus be rewritten as (Woessner & Poeter, 2024):

$$q = -K_1 \frac{\Delta h_1}{d_1} = -K_2 \frac{\Delta h_2}{d_2} = \dots = -K_{M-1} \frac{\Delta h_{M-1}}{d_{M-1}} = -K_M \frac{\Delta h_M}{d_M} = -K_{eq} \frac{\Delta h}{d} \quad (4.2)$$

where $\Delta h_m(\text{m})$ is the hydraulic head difference over the layer thickness $d_m(\text{m})$ occurring within any layer $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$ with the hydraulic conductivity $K_m(\text{m s}^{-1})$. Since q is constant, then the same holds for the entire soil column where $\Delta h(\text{m})$ is the hydraulic head difference over the entire soil column of thickness $d(\text{m})$ with the equivalent hydraulic conductivity $K_{eq}(\text{m s}^{-1})$. The latter is given as (Woessner & Poeter, 2024):

$$K_{eq} = \frac{d}{\sum_{m=1}^M \frac{d_m}{K_m}} \quad (4.3)$$

Conceptually, soil layers with a low K are expected to exert the primary forcing on the groundwater flow within a single soil column. This is also reflected in eq. (4.3) as it is calculated as a thickness-weighted harmonic mean. When the vertical hydraulic gradients at a specific locations are known, the hydraulic flux rates can be calculated as:

$$q = -K_{eq} \frac{dh}{dz} \quad (4.4)$$

The obtained q estimates for each GWT point are listed in Table 4.4. Note that in the final calculation, fully saturated conditions were assumed across the entire soil column, since the depth to the groundwater table is rather shallow for most of the GWT points (see Table 4.1). This lead to d in Equation (4.3) being the total depth z of the GWT point in question (see Table 4.1). Furthermore, most GWT points do not have an adjacent piezometer with which $\Delta h/\Delta L$ could be calculated. As such, the mean $\Delta h/\Delta L$ estimates according to topographical unit were used (see Table 4.3).

GWT point	$K_{eq}(\text{m s}^{-1})$	$q(\text{m s}^{-1})$
5097	$6.5E - 09$	$2E - 10$
6007	$3.1E - 09$	$2.2E - 11$
6022	$3.7E - 09$	$2.6E - 11$
6039	$3.2E - 09$	$2.2E - 11$
6078	$4.2E - 07$	$4E - 08$
6125	$3.4E - 09$	$3.2E - 10$
6511	$2.8E - 09$	$8.4E - 11$
7007	$4E - 09$	$2.7E - 11$
7030	$4.8E - 09$	$3.3E - 11$
7040	$2.1E - 09$	$1.9E - 11$
7043	$1.5E - 09$	$1.3E - 11$
7056	$5E - 08$	$4.4E - 10$
8055	$2.3E - 09$	$1.6E - 11$
8061	$3.2E - 09$	$2.2E - 11$
8200	$2.1E - 09$	$6.4E - 11$
8215	$5.1E - 09$	$1.5E - 10$

Table 4.4: Estimated K_{eq} and q values for all the 16 GWT points

4.2.4 Surface temperatures

In total there are 11 meteorological stations in the Berlin area, that have been recording AST and precipitation on a timescale of 20 years or more, since 1964. In addition, GST down to a depth of 100 cm is being derived using air temperature, wind velocity, relative humidity, precipitation and solar radiation for 5 of these locations, dating back to 1991. Lastly, GST is being measured down to a depth of 85 cm on 23 separate locations with the first station operating since 2019. The number of candidate stations is presented in Table 4.5. Given the aforementioned constraints on the available data, the following approach was taken in order to derive GST estimates:

- Seasonal GST variability at the depth of 5 cm was estimated using measured GST data available from 2021 onward, as earlier observations are too sparse.
- Multi-annual GST variability since 1991 at the depth of 5 cm was estimated based on the derived GST data.
- Multi-annual GST variability prior to 1991 at the depth of 5 cm was estimated using AST data as a proxy.

Partition	Category	AST		GST	GWT
				mes.	der.
Area Type	Commercial	4	4	1	6
	Residential	4	7	3	3
	Green	3	12	1	7
Surface Imper.	< 20%	6	14	3	8
	20 – 40%	1	2	0	2
	40 – 60%	2	1	2	1
	60 – 80%	2	0	0	2
	> 80%	0	6	0	3

Table 4.5: Number of monitoring points recording AST, GST (measured and derived) and GWT, per different UHI unit

In order to account for the UHI effect and how it translates onto estimates of both AST and GST, the study area was partitioned according to (see Figure 4.4):

- by **Area Type**

- Green Areas (forests, grassland, agricultural land, any type of land providing an impervious surface)
- Residential Areas (urban built-up areas with a discontinuous urban fabric)
- Commercial Areas (urban built-up land with a continuous urban fabric (more than 80 % building coverage), industrial and commercial land, any type of traffic land including roads, highways, railways, and airports)

- by **Surface Imperviousness**

Figure 4.4: Land cover partition of the study area according to A) area type (European Environment Agency, 2020a) and B) surface imperviousness (European Environment Agency, 2020b) with the position of the corresponding monitoring points (Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD), 2019, 2024; Senate Department for the Environment, n.d.)

An estimate on the reliability of the derived GST values was obtained by comparing measured and derived values of GST between the years 2021 and 2024 for all different surface area partition units. Two clear outliers were found for less impervious surfaces, namely green areas and surfaces with < 20 % imperviousness (see Table 4.6). The observed discrepancy however, can also be attributed to the over-representation of the measured GST data with respect to the derived GST data in these areas (see Table 4.5). Overall derived GST values are on average higher than measured ones as indicated by ΔGST in Table 4.6. Although the partition by surface imperviousness is limited in scope, it displays more reliable results as indicated by lower RMSE and MSE estimates.

A seasonal variability in GST is observed on the more impervious surfaces while on a multi-annual timescale no major differences can be observed between the different surface area partition units (see Figure 4.5). Moreover, all surface area partition units display an increase of approximately 3 °C between the years of 1991 and 2024, indicating a trend that is in line with observed AST trends.

Partition	Category	RMSE	MSE	$\Delta\overline{\text{GST}}$
Area Type	Commercial	0.18	0.03	0.03
	Residential	0.96	0.93	0.93
	Green	1.72	2.95	1.70
Surface Imper.	< 20%	1.38	1.92	1.38
	40 – 60%	0.49	0.24	0.44

Table 4.6: Error estimates of the derived GST at depth of 5 cm on a multi-annual and the seasonal timescale for the different surface area partition units. $\Delta\overline{\text{GST}}$ is given as the arithmetic mean of $\Delta\text{GST} = \text{GST}(\text{mes.}) - \text{GST}(\text{der.})$

Figure 4.5: Derived GST multi-annual trends since 1991 (left) and measured seasonal GST trends since 2021 (right).

On longer timescales, GST trends have been shown to mirror those of AST (Smerdon et al., 2006). This allows for the estimation of GST values before 1991 based on available AST data. A multi-annual relationship was established by analysing the difference between GST and AST trends, i.e. $\Delta\text{ST} = \text{GST} - \text{AST}$. Both AST and GST trends follow a similar path, which leads to ΔST being rather monotonous over time. Moreover, GST is observed to be on average higher than AST, with the difference slightly increasing over time, as indicated by a tilt of the ΔST trend-lines. Similar to what discussed before, the partition by surface imperviousness displays slightly better results as indicated by the smaller standard deviation of the ΔST trend-lines (see Figure 4.6).

Due to the slight tilt of the ΔST trend-lines, a linearly fitted curve was chosen to reconstruct historical GST records. The resulting AST-GST relationship was established over a period of more than 30 years, making it suitable for reconstruction of the historical GST trends for a couple of decades leading up 1991 (Smerdon et al., 2006; note that the oldest GWT records date back only to 1978, see Table 4.1). Lastly, the reconstructed GST shows a general warming trend consistent with that derived for GST since 1991, pointing to reasonable results (see Figure 4.7).

Figure 4.6: Multi-annual comparison of the derived GST values with AST values for the different surface area partition units. Note that the difference is given as $\Delta ST = GST - AST$

Figure 4.7: GST prior to 1991 predicted from AST values (left of the red line) and derived GST since 1991 (right of the red line)

4.3 Results

The performance of the analytical solution to the advection–dispersion equation (ADE) given in (3.64) in reproducing GWT dynamics under climate change was assessed by comparing simulated and measured GWT profiles. The GWT profiles were simulated using all three types of bottom boundary conditions, namely Dirichlet ($\alpha = 1$, $\alpha^* = 0$), Neumann ($\alpha = 0$, $\alpha^* = k_M$) and Robin ($\alpha = 1$, $\alpha^* = k_M$). To isolate the error introduced by the assumption of fully saturated conditions across the entire soil column, separate RMSE values were calculated for the regions above and below the multi-annual mean groundwater table depth \bar{z}_{GW} , denoted as $RMSE(x \leq \bar{z}_{GW})$ and $RMSE(x > \bar{z}_{GW})$, respectively (see Table 4.1 and Figure 4.8). The total error across all depths is labeled as $RMSE(\forall x)$. All RMSE metrics are reported as the average over all simulated GWT profiles (aggregated across all time steps). Additionally, to examine the influence of vertical geological heterogeneity, the model was applied in two configurations - a layered setup using layer-specific soil parameters, and an equivalent setup employing the following harmonically averaged parameters:

$$\lambda_{eq} = \frac{x_M}{\sum_{m=1}^M \frac{d_m}{\lambda_{b,m}}}; \quad C_{b,eq} = \frac{x_M}{\sum_{m=1}^M \frac{d_m}{C_{b,m}}}. \quad (4.5)$$

Both setups considered the same set of BCs and ICs. All GWT profiles were simulated using the first 100 terms in the eigenvalue series, and the parameter k_m was set to $\lambda_{b,m}$ (Pérez Guerrero et al., 2013). The solution with Robin BC yielded the best overall results and, as such, only the outcomes obtained with this BC are discussed further (see Table 4.7).

GWT point	\bar{z}_{GW}	RMSE										
		F_m	Layered					Equivalent				
			$\forall x$	$x > \bar{z}_{GW}$	$x \leq \bar{z}_{GW}$	t_0	t_N	$\forall x$	$x > \bar{z}_{GW}$	$x \leq \bar{z}_{GW}$	t_0	t_N
6511	4.06	0.04	0.88	0.88	0.31	2.32	0.36	0.75	0.75	0.35	1.89	0.35
5097	9.09	0.01	0.92	0.88	2.12	1.08	0.78	0.83	0.79	2.12	0.74	0.77
8200	1.23	0.01	0.98	0.98	1.00	0.93	1.02	0.92	0.91	1.02	0.76	0.98
6078	15.22	0.98	1.05	0.82	1.43	2.48	0.11	1.10	0.91	1.41	2.68	0.08
6125	12.21	0.00	1.05	0.97	1.44	2.72	0.51	0.73	0.65	1.47	1.42	0.52
8215	-0.29	0.00	1.12	1.12	-	0.89	0.22	1.10	1.10	-	0.81	0.21
8061	2.86	0.01	1.22	1.22	-	1.90	0.90	1.16	1.16	-	1.57	0.91
6007	4.78	0.24	1.50	1.47	2.60	1.99	1.23	1.50	1.46	2.45	2.04	1.23
7007	2.98	0.09	1.57	1.55	2.51	1.69	1.81	1.45	1.43	2.44	1.43	1.79
7030	4.06	0.02	1.60	1.57	4.14	1.01	1.70	1.58	1.54	4.54	0.74	1.68
8055	5.63	0.08	1.61	1.64	0.82	2.71	1.13	1.15	1.17	0.69	1.73	0.84
6022	5.50	0.02	1.89	1.87	2.05	1.53	1.69	1.90	1.88	2.11	1.49	1.75
7056	30.95	0.04	1.93	1.95	0.31	3.40	1.24	1.69	1.71	0.33	2.43	1.18
6039	5.99	0.11	2.02	2.01	2.20	2.55	2.31	2.21	2.18	2.60	2.78	2.55
7040	12.24	0.00	3.38	3.32	8.25	5.79	2.78	2.23	2.14	8.06	2.90	1.89
7043	3.27	0.03	5.13	5.13	2.48	8.67	4.02	1.69	1.69	1.63	2.03	1.64
Avg.	7.49	0.11	1.74	1.71	2.26	2.60	1.36	1.37	1.34	2.23	1.71	1.15

Table 4.7: RMSE estimates for Robin ($\alpha = 1$, $\alpha^* = k_M$) for a layered and an equivalent setup. \bar{z}_{GW} is the multi-annual mean groundwater table depth, F_m is the RMSE of the piece-wise linearly defined initial GWT profile at initial time, $\forall x, \leq x_{GW}$ and $> x_{GW}$ are the RMSE defined in the respective regions (see Section 4.3), t_0 is the RMSE of the F_m simulated with the CITT solution, t_N is the RMSE of the simulated profile at the final time

A representative example of the simulated GWT profiles against the measured ones is portrayed in Figure 4.8. Two clear outliers in terms of RMSE were observed, namely the GWT points 7040 and 7043. As such, these two points are taken out of consideration and are discussed separately in Section 4.3.1. As expected, the error was generally the greatest in the first simulated profile, i.e. $RMSE(t_0)$. This behaviour for the most part is attributed to the exponential smoothing of the solution (3.64) as $t \rightarrow \infty$ (see Table 4.7).

Figure 4.8: Simulated (solid lines) and measured (markers) GWT profiles for the GWT point 6078 with Robin BC on the outlet.

GWT points with a shallower \bar{z}_{GW} exhibited slightly higher error estimates than those with a deeper \bar{z}_{GW} , though a consistent pattern is hardly to be determined due to the limited sample size. A clearer pattern was observed when fluctuations in groundwater levels were considered — GWT points with less variation in \bar{z}_{GW} (i.e., a lower standard deviation) showed more consistent error estimates. Interestingly, points with a shallower \bar{z}_{GW} displayed higher $RMSE(x > \bar{z}_{GW})$, in both absolute terms and relative to $RMSE(\forall x)$.

Figure 4.9: RMSE in respect to A) \bar{z}_{GW} and B) its' standard deviation $std(\bar{z}_{GW})$ for an equivalent and a layered setup. The overall mean RMSE values (excluding GWT points 7040 and 7043) are provided on the right side of the figure, next to their respective markers.

Overall, the $RMSE(\forall x)$ values are relatively consistent across all area types, while a clearer trend emerges for $RMSE(x \leq \bar{z}_{GW})$ (see Figure 4.10). No distinct pattern is apparent when grouping by surface imperviousness, which may be attributed to the limited number of GWT points per each unit. When analyzed by topographical unit — with the exception of the single GWT point on the Teltow Plateau — the largest $RMSE(\forall x)$ is observed in the Warsaw-Berlin Spillway, which also exhibits the highest $RMSE(x \leq \bar{z}_{GW})$. It is worth noting that five of the seven GWT points are situated in commercial areas, while three are located beneath surfaces with more than 80 % imperviousness, and these points similarly show some of the highest overall RMSE values. This may suggest a relationship between higher surface imperviousness and greater GWT uncertainty, particularly in the unsaturated zone. This, combined with the fact that the GWT points in the Warsaw-Berlin Spillway have a very shallow \bar{z}_{GW} , could help explain the elevated RMSE observed for this topographical unit.

Figure 4.10: RMSE in respect to A) the Topographical Unit (TP: Teltow Plateau; WBS: Warsaw-Berlin Spillway; BP: Barnim Plateau; PV: Panke Valley), B) Area Type (G: Green; R: Residential; C: Commercial) and C) Surface Imperviousness level (1: $<20\%$; 2: $20 - 40\%$; 3: $40 - 60\%$; 4: $60 - 80\%$; 5: $\geq 80\%$). The provided bars represent the average RMSE for all simulated GWT profiles in a respective GWT point obtained within an equivalent and a layered setup, while the number on top of the bars represent the number of GWT points in the respective unit. The overall mean RMSE values (excluding GWT points 7040 and 7043) are provided on the right side of the figure, next to their respective markers.

A comparison of the two modeling approaches revealed that the equivalent setup performed marginally better when the two outliers are not considered (see Figure 4.9 and 4.10). In contrast, a substantial improvement was observed for the two outliers themselves (see Table 4.7) reducing the overall $RMSE(\forall x)$, $RMSE(x \leq \bar{z}_{GW})$ and $RMSE(x > \bar{z}_{GW})$ by 2.3, 0.5 and 2.3, respectively. While seemingly counterintu-

itive, this result highlights a critical challenge when considering a layered setup — the performance gain from increased complexity can be easily offset by uncertainties in the definition of the layer-specific soil parameters. This is further discussed in Section 5.1.

4.3.1 Outliers

The two outliers — GWT points 7040 and 7043 (see Table 4.7) — are both located on the Teltow plateau, beneath a surface with $\leq 20\%$ imperviousness. On the other hand, 7040 lies in a residential setting, while 7043 is situated in a green area. Although 7040 shows a slightly lower overall $\text{RMSE}(\forall x)$ than 7043, both points exhibit a much better performance under the equivalent setup compared to the layered one. Specifically, $\text{RMSE}(\forall x)$ is reduced by approximately 1.15 for 7040 and 3.44 for 7043. Similar improvements are observed for $\text{RMSE}(x > \bar{z}_{GW})$, while marginal gains of around 0.19 and 0.85 are noticed for $\text{RMSE}(x \leq \bar{z}_{GW})$, respectively. The overall better performance of the equivalent setup can clearly be observed in Figure 4.11.

Figure 4.11: Simulated GWT profiles for the outlier GWT points A) 7040 and B) 7043 in a layered and equivalent setup in comparison to the measured GWT

However, the larger errors at these two points cannot be explained simply by their groundwater depth characteristics. For instance, \bar{z}_{GW} is situated at the depth of 12.24 m at the point 7040 and at the depth of 3.27 m at the point 7043. On the other hand, the variability $\text{std}(\bar{z}_{GW})$ is much below average at both locations. The very high error for these two points thus runs counter to the trends observed in Figure 4.9. Similarly, land use and surface impermeability offer little explanatory power. Although both points lie beneath surfaces with $\leq 20\%$ imperviousness — observed to having the lowest $\text{RMSE}(x \leq \bar{z}_{GW})$ values (see Figure 4.10) — point 7040 exhibits a $\text{RMSE}(x \leq \bar{z}_{GW})$ roughly 3.3 times higher than point 7043. Conversely, despite being in a green area — observed to have slightly lower errors than residential areas — point 7043 shows an overall $\text{RMSE}(\forall x)$ that is approximately 52% higher. Only when considering topography do the results become somewhat more consistent — both outliers lie within the Teltow plateau, where $\text{RMSE}(\forall x)$ were observed to be the highest. However, using solely this classification is too vague to be conclusive. A more detailed analysis is thus needed in order to fully explain the obtained results (see Chapter 5).

Chapter 5

Discussion

Despite the limited sample size, certain general trends in solution accuracy can still be identified. As shown in Figure 4.9, the error tends to increase steadily with greater fluctuation in \bar{z}_{GW} . Conversely, points with a shallower \bar{z}_{GW} exhibited higher error estimates compared to those with deeper water tables. As observed by Tsy-pin et al., 2024, the meteorological precipitation signal gets damped with depth, implying that a shallower aquifer experiences a greater variability in groundwater levels. This, in turn, leads to more pronounced temporal and spatial variations in Darcy flux q . In our solution, advection in Equation (2.1) is assumed to be constant. Therefore, the higher error estimates at locations with shallower \bar{z}_{GW} are likely attributable to the assumption of steady flow.

Nonetheless, the GWT point with the deepest \bar{z}_{GW} — the point 7056, represented by the rightmost point in Figure 4.9 A) — points to an increasing error trend. This suggests that beyond a certain \bar{z}_{GW} , the error begins to rise again. A plausible explanation is the presence of a thicker unsaturated zone, which exhibits heat transport properties distinct from those of the saturated zone, even though the model assumes fully saturated conditions across the entire soil column. The error is thus expected to be minimized when \bar{z}_{GW} lies within an approximate range of 10 to 20 m. In this interval, the groundwater table is deep enough for the precipitation signals to be sufficiently smoothed out, yet shallow enough for heat transport to remain dominated by saturated conditions. It should be noted, however, that for thicker unsaturated zones, the parameters in the solution derived in Section 3.3 — particularly C_b — can be adjusted to better approximate unsaturated conditions (see Section 5.1).

In the context of area type (see Figure 4.10 B), the observed increase in $\text{RMSE}(x \leq \bar{z}_{GW})$ can largely be attributed to the limited sample size. For instance, five out of six GWT points in commercial areas are also situated within the Warsaw-Berlin Spillway — a topographical unit associated with the highest $\text{RMSE}(x \leq \bar{z}_{GW})$. Conversely, five out of six GWT points located in green areas fall outside the spillway. A similar pattern holds if based on a classification by surface imperviousness (see Table 4.1). As a result, no conclusive relationship between surface characteristics and solution accuracy can be drawn from the available data.

Nevertheless, groundwater levels provide a more reliable basis for error characterization than area type or surface imperviousness. In more urbanised areas, surface cover is often fragmented, with natural surfaces and impervious urban features all being present within a small extent of an area. This results in a highly localised hydrological behaviour that often cannot be captured by simple urbanisation or imperviousness metrics alone. For example, Miller and Hess, 2017 found that surface runoff on fragmented suburban surfaces behaves differently from that on continuous rural surfaces, even when imperviousness and other urbanisation-hydrological metrics are very similar. This limitation is further illustrated by two GWT points found within the 20 – 40% imperviousness class. Point 7030 is located next to a main road in a densely populated residential area within the Berlin city limits, while point 8061 lies on a large grass patch in the suburban outskirts of Berlin. Despite sharing same imperviousness values, their hydrological behaviour is expected to be substantially different. In addition, the presence of underground structures in heavily urbanised areas can further distort local hydrology and the shallow subsurface temperature field (Böttcher & Zosseder, 2022; D’Aniello et al., 2021; Noethen et al., 2023). Together, these factors underscore the limitations of relying on surface imperviousness or area type to explain variations in solution accuracy.

That being said, the presence of two outliers suggests that the error is not solely governed by \bar{z}_{GW} (see Section 4.3.1), and therefore further analysis is required. As shown in Figure 4.11, both outliers are characterised by heterogeneous soil profiles consisting of numerous thin, alternating layers of aquifer and

aquitard soil types. This suggests that large parameter variations over short distances may contribute to higher error estimates. A convenient way to quantify such variability is the weighted L1 gradient norm, centered at the layer midpoints $(\tilde{x}_{m-1} + \tilde{x}_m)/2$; $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$. For \tilde{U}_m it is given as

$$\left\| \frac{\Delta \tilde{U}}{\Delta \tilde{x}} \right\|_1 = 2 \sum_{m=1}^{M-1} \left| \frac{\tilde{U}_{m+1} - \tilde{U}_m}{\tilde{x}_{m+1} - \tilde{x}_{m-1}} \right| \quad (5.1)$$

Examining Figure 5.1 reveals that $\text{RMSE}(\forall x)$ is primarily influenced by sharp transitions in the non-dimensional diffusivity \tilde{D}_m between adjacent layers. In contrast, variability in \tilde{U}_m and \tilde{k}_m appears to have a comparatively weaker correlation with the error. This also potentially explains why the equivalent solution setup displayed greatly improved results for the two outliers, as the jumps in \tilde{D}_m are minimal. A similar pattern is observed for $\text{RMSE}(x > \bar{z}_{GW})$, however no clear trend can be observed for $\text{RMSE}(x \leq \bar{z}_{GW})$. This points to an over-representation of thin layers with large jumps in \tilde{D}_m , introducing localized discrepancies that propagate through the solution. This issue can, however, be mitigated by adjusting the heat transport parameters assigned to the layers, thereby improving the solution accuracy (see Section 5.1).

Figure 5.1: RMSE in respect to the weighted L1 gradient norm of A) \tilde{U}_m B) \tilde{D}_m and C) \tilde{k}_m for all GWT points, including the two outliers 7040 and 7043

5.1 Parameter optimization

Among the soil parameters, thermal conductivity λ_b is the only parameter that was measured specifically within the study area. It is therefore assumed to carry the least amount of uncertainty. In contrast, hydraulic conductivity K and bulk volumetric heat capacity C_b are sourced from general geological reports and industry standards where they are typically provided within broad ranges, making them the primary candidates for optimization.

Defining K individually for each layer is, however, not necessary. As shown in Section 4.2.3, the layer-specific values K_m collectively influence the solution through a single term — the vertical hydraulic flux q . This flux can be estimated using several methods, each with its own limitations and sources of uncertainty (Irvine et al., 2017). A common approach involves estimating flow rates from measured GWT profiles by fitting a solution of the ADE (2.1) to the observed data (Irvine et al., 2017; Kurylyk & Irvine, 2016; Lin et al., 2022). Following this principle, the flux rates q initially estimated in Section 4.2.3 were optimized using the `minimize` function from `SciPy`, employing the L-BFGS-B method in the range of 0.1% and 1000% of the original q to minimize the overall RMSE for each GWT point. This adjustment, however, had only a minor effect on the overall RMSE — yielding an improvement of only 1.08 and 0.03 for the two outliers 7040 and 7043 respectively.

The limited impact of adjusting q alone suggests that the dominant source of error lies in the uncertainty associated with the C_b estimates. Furthermore, unlike q , C_b appears in both the advection and diffusion terms of the ADE (2.1), making it a highly influential solution parameter (see Chapter 2). The values of C_b across all layers were subsequently optimized using the same method with each parameter constrained to the range of 0.3 to 4.0 MJ m^{-3} . By doing so, the accuracy of the solution was greatly improved as indicated by the lower RMSE values provided in Table 5.1 and as can be observed in Figure 5.2.

GWT point	RMSE				
	$\forall x$	$x > \bar{z}_{GW}$	$x \leq \bar{z}_{GW}$	t_0	t_N
7040	0.83	5.15	0.69	4.18	0.13
7043	0.36	1.27	0.35	1.62	0.20

Table 5.1: RMSE estimates for the two outlier GWT points 7040 and 7043 with optimized $C_{b,m}$ values for $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$

Figure 5.2: Simulated GWT profiles for the outlier GWT points A) 7040 and B) 7043 with optimized $C_{b,m}$ values

5.2 Limitations and Future studies

The first limitation of the present study stems from the limited sample size of available GWT points. While the solution displayed promising results for certain types of sites, it remains unclear for which specific site characteristics it performs best and yields the most trustworthy predictions. By relying on a larger statistical base, various regression techniques — e.g. support vector machines and other machine learning models — could be applied to uncover underlying influences on solution accuracy and to identify key controlling parameters. Such an approach would help determine for which types of sites the proposed solution is most reliable. That being said, there are over two hundred GWT monitoring points within the study area. Although most are shallower than the points considered in Section 4.3, they could still contribute substantially to the statistical base, potentially enabling a more quantitative validation of the patterns discussed in Chapter 5. Moreover, this approach could be extended to include additional sites beyond the study area.

Secondly, as observed in Figure 4.9 and subsequently noted in Chapter 5, assuming a constant hydraulic flux q may lead to substantial errors at sites where the groundwater table exhibits significant variability. For this reason, incorporating spatially and temporally variable coefficients into the solution — namely $D_m(x, t)$ and $U_m(x, t)$ — could greatly improve the model accuracy. Furthermore, such an approach would allow the model to capture transient changes in soil parameters, in particular the switch between saturated and unsaturated conditions in response to recharge driven by precipitation. Cotta et al., 2020 have derived a solution for a problem similar to the one described in Equation (3.1) that accommodates spatially dependent coefficients. A possible simple formulation that includes temporal dependence is to assume that the coefficients can be decomposed into a baseline component and a transient component driven by recharge. Mathematically, this would write as

$$D_m(x, t) = D_{b,m}(x) + {}^D C_m f(t) D_{t,m}(x); \quad U_m(x, t) = U_{b,m}(x) + {}^U C_m f(t) U_{t,m}(x) \quad (5.2)$$

where $D_{b,m}(x)$ and $U_{b,m}(x)$ represent the baseline coefficients, $f(t)$ is a time-dependent function describing the precipitation forcing, $D_{t,m}(x)$ and $U_{t,m}(x)$ capture the spatial patterns of the transient response, and ${}^D C_m$ and ${}^U C_m$ are scaling coefficients that determine the magnitude of the transient effect on each coefficient. This separated form allows the transient component to be factored out while

preserving the spatial heterogeneity of the response. With appropriate assumptions on the form of $f(t)$, such a formulation could, in principle, be incorporated into the analytical framework of Cotta et al., 2020. However, careful analysis would be required to determine whether the linear scaling with precipitation adequately captures the underlying physics, or whether more sophisticated coupling between D_m , U_m , and precipitation is necessary. Furthermore, this could potentially be coupled with the work done by Hayek, 2016. It is also noted that the solution derived by Cotta et al., 2020 can readily be adapted for 2D or 3D applications.

Lastly, as noted in Section 4.3, the solution begins to display nonphysical behaviour for large Péclet numbers. This behaviour is caused by the large exponent in the EVP solution (3.36). From a mathematical standpoint, however, this is to be expected — for $Pe \gg 1 \implies U \gg D$ the ADE (2.1) becomes a singularly perturbed PDE. In a similar fashion, while considering a single-layer system, Van Genuchten and Alves, 1982 proposed that for cases where $Pe > 5 + 40\tilde{t} \vee Pe > 100$ approximate solutions should be used. An approximate solution to such a problem can be obtained in a relatively straightforward manner using the method of matched asymptotics. Employing this method, Amirat and Münch, 2020 derived an approximate solution to the ADE (2.1) in a single homogeneous layer. Their work could potentially be extended to the multi-layer ADE problem (3.1), providing a solution for cases where advection is the dominant heat transport mechanism.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

The following conclusions can be drawn regarding the two main objectives outlined in Section 1.4:

- A flexible and computationally efficient analytical solution for one-dimensional heat transport in a multi-layer stratified porous medium was successfully derived and subsequently parameterized using high-resolution geological profiles and historical surface temperature records.
- The influence of high-resolution vertical geological profiles on the prediction accuracy was successfully assessed relative to a harmonically averaged parameterization of the entire soil column.

and regarding the **main scientific question**:

- The proposed analytical solution, when combined with high-resolution vertical geological profiles, can indeed produce accurate and computationally efficient predictions of the shallow subsurface temperature field evolution. However, this approach may become counterproductive when layer-specific soil parameters are not constrained within relatively narrow ranges, as demonstrated by the overall superior performance of the harmonically averaged homogeneous parametrization. For sites where subsurface temperature data are available, this limitation can potentially be mitigated through parameter fitting. Nevertheless, the findings also highlight areas for future improvement. A larger statistical database would enable the use of data analytic techniques to identify key controlling parameters and to determine for which site characteristics the solution performs best. Furthermore, extending the solution to accommodate spatially and temporally variable coefficients could improve accuracy at sites with significant groundwater table fluctuations, while the development of approximate solutions for advection-dominated regimes could address the observed nonphysical behaviour at high Péclet numbers. Addressing these aspects could advance the presented model toward a generally applicable framework.

Chapter 7

Supplementary Materials

A General solution via Laplace transform

The relatively simple closed form solution to the ADE in a homogeneous finite domain, with zero IC, linearly increasing Dirichlet BC on the inlet and zero Dirichlet BC on the outlet is easily obtainable with the help of the Laplace transform. Mathematically this setup writes as

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{T}}{\partial \tilde{t}} = \tilde{D} \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{T}}{\partial \tilde{x}^2} - \frac{\partial \tilde{T}}{\partial \tilde{x}} = \tilde{L} \tilde{T}; \quad 0 \leq \tilde{x} \leq 1 \quad (\text{A.1})$$

with zero IC, i.e. $\tilde{T}(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t} = 0) = 0$ and the following BC

$$\tilde{T} = \tilde{v}_0(\tilde{t}) = \tilde{p}_0 + \tilde{p}_1 \tilde{t}; \quad \tilde{x} = 0 \quad (\text{A.2a})$$

$$\tilde{T} = 0; \quad \tilde{x} = 1 \quad (\text{A.2b})$$

First, the Laplace transform \mathcal{L} is applied to eq. (A.1) in respect to \tilde{t} as such

$$\bar{T}(x, s) = \mathcal{L}\{\tilde{T}(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t})\} = \int_0^\infty e^{-s\tilde{t}} \tilde{T}(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t}) d\tilde{t} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

resulting in eq. (A.1) becoming a second order ODE, namely

$$\tilde{D} \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{T}}{\partial \tilde{x}^2} - \frac{\partial \tilde{T}}{\partial \tilde{x}} - s\tilde{T} = 0; \quad 0 \leq \tilde{x} \leq 1 \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Applying the Laplace transform to the BC does not induce any change to (A.2b), while on the other hand (A.2a) becomes

$$\tilde{v}_0(s) = \frac{\tilde{p}_0}{s} + \frac{\tilde{p}_1}{s^2} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

The general solution to eq. (A.4) is given as

$$\bar{T}(\tilde{x}, s) = \left[C_1 \sinh(\beta(s) \cdot \tilde{x}) + C_2 \cosh(\beta(s) \cdot \tilde{x}) \right] e^{\gamma \tilde{x}} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{2\tilde{D}}; \quad \beta(s) = \sqrt{\gamma^2 + \frac{s}{\tilde{D}}} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Plugging in the BC (A.2a) and (A.2b) the coefficients C_1 and C_2 are determined by solving the following system of equations

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ \sinh(\beta(s)) & \cosh(\beta(s)) \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{v}_0(s) \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

The determinant of the matrix on the LHS of eq. (A.8) is $-\sinh(\beta(s))$, which translates to the coefficients C_1 and C_2 being determined by

$$C_1 = -s \frac{\cosh(\beta(s))}{s \sinh(\beta(s))} \tilde{v}_0(s); \quad C_2 = s \frac{\sinh(\beta(s))}{s \sinh(\beta(s))} \tilde{v}_0(s) \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Using the hyperbolic identity $\sinh(A \pm B) = \sinh(A) \cosh(B) \pm \cosh(A) \sinh(B)$ eq. (A.6) can be rewritten as

$$\bar{T}(\tilde{x}, s) = s \tilde{v}_0(s) \frac{\sinh(\beta(s) \cdot (1 - \tilde{x}))}{s \sinh(\beta(s))} \exp(\gamma \tilde{x}) \quad (\text{A.10})$$

This expression can be inverted back to the \tilde{t} domain using the inverse Laplace transform \mathcal{L}^{-1} via a combination of the residue theorem and the convolution theorem. The rational function in eq. (A.10) is first inverted via the residue theorem giving

$$g(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t}) = \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left(\frac{\sinh(\beta(s) \cdot (1 - \tilde{x}))}{s \sinh(\beta(s))} \right) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \lim_{s \rightarrow s_i} \frac{\sinh(\beta(s) \cdot (1 - \tilde{x}))}{\frac{d}{ds} [s \sinh(\beta(s))]} e^{s \tilde{t}} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

where s_i are the poles of $s \sinh(\beta(s))$. The expression has a single real pole at $s_r = 0$ and an infinite series of complex poles s_j ; $j = 0, 1 \dots \infty$ which give rise to $\beta(s_j) = i \tilde{\beta}_j$ where i is the imaginary unit. These poles must satisfy the following

$$\sinh(\beta(s_j)) = 0 \implies \sin(\tilde{\beta}_j) = 0 \quad j = 0, 1 \dots \infty \quad (\text{A.12})$$

implying that $\tilde{\beta}_j = j\pi$; $j = 0, 1, \dots \infty$ resulting in the following definition for the complex poles

$$s_j = -\tilde{D} \left(\gamma^2 + j^2 \pi^2 \right) \quad (\text{A.13})$$

Furthermore the following simplifications can be made

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{ds} [s \sinh(\beta(s))] &= \sinh(\gamma); & s = s_r \\ \frac{d}{ds} [s \sinh(\beta(s))] &= -\frac{(\gamma^2 + j^2 \pi^2) (-1)^j}{2i j \pi}; & s = s_j, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots \infty \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.14})$$

resulting in eq. (A.11) becoming

$$g(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t}) = \frac{\sinh(\gamma(1 - \tilde{x}))}{\sinh(\gamma)} - 2\pi \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{j \sin(j\pi \tilde{x})}{\gamma^2 + j^2 \pi^2} e^{-\tilde{D}(\gamma^2 + j^2 \pi^2) \tilde{t}} \quad (\text{A.15})$$

Furthermore, the inverse of $s \tilde{v}_0(s)$ is given as

$$f(\tilde{t}) = \mathcal{L}^{-1} (s \tilde{v}_0(s)) = \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left(\tilde{p}_0 + \frac{\tilde{p}_1}{s} \right) = \tilde{p}_0 \delta(\tilde{t}) + \tilde{p}_1 \quad (\text{A.16})$$

where $\delta(\tilde{t})$ is the Dirac delta function. Finally a product of two separately inverted functions is combined via the convolution theorem as such

$$\tilde{T}(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t}) = \mathcal{L}^{-1} (\bar{T}(\tilde{x}, s)) = e^{\gamma \tilde{x}} (f * g)(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t}) = e^{\gamma \tilde{x}} \int_0^{\tilde{t}} f(\tau) g(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t} - \tau) d\tau \quad (\text{A.17})$$

leading to the following closed form solution

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{T}(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t}) &= \tilde{p}_0 \left[\frac{\sinh(\gamma(1 - \tilde{x}))}{\sinh(\gamma)} - 2\pi \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{j \sin(j\pi \tilde{x})}{\gamma^2 + j^2 \pi^2} e^{-\tilde{D}(\gamma^2 + j^2 \pi^2) \tilde{t}} \right] e^{\gamma \tilde{x}} \\ &+ \tilde{p}_1 \left[\frac{\sinh(\gamma(1 - \tilde{x}))}{\sinh(\gamma)} \tilde{t} - \frac{2\pi}{\tilde{D}} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{j \sin(j\pi \tilde{x})}{(\gamma^2 + j^2 \pi^2)^2} \left(1 - e^{-\tilde{D}(\gamma^2 + j^2 \pi^2) \tilde{t}} \right) \right] e^{\gamma \tilde{x}} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.18})$$

It is noted that for the case of a constant temperature on the inlet, i.e. when $\tilde{p}_1 = 0$, the obtained solution is in line with the solution derived by Davis, 1985. On the other hand, note that the obtained solution can be reformulated such that it is aligned with the steady state solution to eq. (3.18). In the

context of the BC eq. (3.19a) this leads to $\tilde{p}_0 \rightarrow 1$ and $\tilde{p}_1 \rightarrow 0$. The alternative steady state solution $\bar{\Phi}(\tilde{x})$ to eq. (3.18) is then obtained by letting $\tilde{t} \rightarrow \infty$ in eq. (A.18) leading to

$$\bar{\Phi}(\tilde{x}) = \lim_{\tilde{t} \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{T}(\tilde{x}, \tilde{t}) = \frac{\sinh(\gamma(1 - \tilde{x}))}{\sinh(\gamma)} \quad (\text{A.19})$$

B Code Availability

The Python 3 code used in this study is openly available and can be accessed through the following GitHub repository: https://github.com/markgrmek/ADE_CITT.

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